

Pilot Study Report on

Daily Living Experiences of People Living with Sickle Cell in Ireland

**Impact on Education
and Employment**

Edited by

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2015 - 2024
INTERNATIONAL DECADE FOR PEOPLE OF
AFRICAN DESCENT
RECOGNITION - JUSTICE - DEVELOPMENT

Abstract

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is a prevalent genetic disorder, particularly in regions like sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East, the Mediterranean and India.

Due to increased immigration, its prevalence in Ireland has risen, yet research on the experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland remains scarce. This study aimed to explore the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland, focusing on their education and employment impacts.

Utilising a qualitative methodology, in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with six participants. Thematic analysis revealed key challenges: inconsistent and often inadequate healthcare access, significant financial burdens, and a lack of awareness among both healthcare providers and the general public.

Participants also highlighted the substantial psychological and social impacts of SCD, including stigma and mental health struggles. Support systems, particularly family involvement, were critical in managing the condition.

The study underscores the urgent need for policy interventions to improve healthcare accessibility, financial support, and public awareness, thereby enhancing the quality of life for individuals with SCD in Ireland

Foreword

Stephen A. McMahon – Co-founder, Irish Patients Association

Listening to patients is the first step to better care

This research is a call to action. It urges policymakers, healthcare providers, and society at large to recognise and address the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with Sickle Cell Disease.

A patient's story is as important as their symptoms, and the insights gained here are not just academic; they are a roadmap for real-world change, aiming to ensure that individuals with SCD receive the holistic and empathetic care they deserve.

Drawing upon the insights from over forty studies, this research meticulously analyses the global and local prevalence of SCD, the physical and psychological challenges it imposes, and the barriers to adequate healthcare.

Two recent studies stand out for their poignant portrayal of patient experiences. In one study, researchers found that the lack of awareness among healthcare providers often resulted in delayed and inadequate treatment, exacerbating the stress and pain experienced by patients (Childerhose et al., 2024). Another study highlighted the profound impact of social stigma and discrimination, revealing that many individuals with SCD felt marginalised and misunderstood by both medical professionals and society at large (Stewart et al., 2021).

I recall the vision of William Mayo, co-founder of the Mayo Clinic in the USA, that "The patient is the centre of the medical universe around which all our work revolves and towards which all our efforts tend," a vision reflected in the guiding principle that still defines the Mayo Clinic today: "The needs of the patient come first."

This research is an echo of the needs for those whose voices often go unheard. It is a testament to the resilience of individuals with SCD and a beacon of hope that their stories will inspire the changes needed to improve theirs and others lives.

I invite you, the many stakeholders, to understand the depth of the challenges faced, where united in our efforts we can make a meaningful difference in the lives of those living with Sickle Cell Disease in Ireland, and indeed in our global neighbourhood.

A big thank you to the authors and all those who participated in this study, and to you the reader.

Irish Patients' Association

Foreword

**Dr Marina Everri – Psychologist and Systemic/Family
Psychotherapist, UCD School of Medicine**

This research project is an in-depth exploration of the everyday life of persons affected by Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), and a significant starting point to raise awareness on the multiple challenges they have experienced across the life-span. Esther and her research team give voice to a group of young adults who take the readers into the complexities of SCD in gentle and sensitive manner, leaving us with a sense of frustration and urgent need to continue to work as researchers and practitioners on this invalidating condition.

SCD is a severe disease that affects individuals' physiology (their body), their psychological process (their mind), and their broader social networks (their family and friends). The pervasiveness of this condition emerged clearly and unanimously from the voices of the participants in this project. Some participants reported challenges in balancing educational commitments with health needs, others reported feeling anxious and distressed for the lack of understanding of the SCD condition not only from their peers and colleagues, but also their GPs. Or, again, others indicated the need to depend from their family carers for their everyday task routines and commitments in a developmental phase – early adulthood – in which the consolidation of independence and autonomy are core for individuals' wellbeing.

Invisibility and stigma emerged as core in participants' stories: SCD symptoms are not visible and there is consistent lack of awareness about the presentation of disease. I was impressed by participants' stories about needing to leave work or college for their hospital appointments and not being understood, and not finding adequate support in those contexts. The perceived barriers to access adequate care and support, which is a core finding of this research study, exacerbate discrimination and stigma and perpetuate SCD invisibility. In this sense, families become central to 'compensate' the lack of perceived support in the healthcare system. The central role of family carers emerged as a core resource across the interviews. Research confirm the centrality of family carers for people affected by chronic diseases; however, if this happens in the absence of adequate support from a policy and service provision perspective, there is a risk for additional burden and stress to the families. In a conference on promoting family support though equality and inclusion that I have attended in Galway recently, researchers and practitioners concluded that in Ireland there is a need to adopt better models for service provision and practice to support and empower families and their members in need. Family is just one of the multiple contexts that persons with SCD inhabit, healthcare service is the other core and significant context.

This research report clearly highlights a need for integration across services (education, social, and healthcare) which, in my view, can only happen when complex conceptual frameworks are taken into account. In other words, we cannot confine SCD to a 'self-contained' medical condition that requires the application of specific medical treatments. The intersectionality of intrapsychic, interpersonal and social cultural variables should be at the core of research and interventions on SCD: gender, race, social class, education, etc. are key factor that should be taken into account when researching and treating SCD. Again, this study shows that individuals live their lives as part of broader systems – families, schools, hospitals, workplaces – and they bring their experiences, their challenges and hopes across these systems. The experience they have in each system impact their well-being. We need more research – and we know that this is core to any good clinical practice and intervention – to develop better models to tackle the complexity of this disease. This can happen only if there is a collaborative effort from different stakeholders: policy makers, legislators, charities and advocacy groups together with researcher and practitioners. My hope is that this study will pave the way for better practices for inclusion and support for children, adults and their families affected by SCD.

Preface

Esther Onolememen – CEO and Founder, Sickle Cell Society Ireland

Embarking on this study has been a profoundly personal and poignant journey, rooted in my lifelong commitment to advocating for individuals living with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD). My experience spans several decades, journeying alongside children and families affected by this challenging condition. This journey began with a deep, personal connection to SCD, driven by the daily realities faced by my own children, plus my experience of my child presenting as one of the first cases of sickle cell. This was at a time when Ireland had a lack of experience with this condition and there was limited knowledge within the public health and social care sectors. This culminating experience led to the founding of the Sickle Cell Society Ireland. This society was established on the premise that rigorous research is crucial in understanding and addressing the complexities of SCD.

Over the years, my passion for advocacy has only intensified. I have witnessed firsthand the myriad struggles that individuals with SCD endure—frequent hospital visits, severe pain crises, psychological burdens, and social stigma. These experiences have fuelled my determination to push for better services, more comprehensive care, and greater awareness. The loss of my daughter to this disease last year was an indescribable personal tragedy, yet it has also reinforced my resolve to continue this vital work. Her memory propels me forward, instilling in me an unyielding zeal to advocate for advancements in SCD treatment and care.

In conducting this research, I took a deliberate step back to empower a new generation of researchers. I trained and supervised six young assistants, guiding them as they ventured into the field to gather data. This approach was not only to ensure the study's rigour but also to foster a culture of learning and passion for SCD research among the youth. I believe that by nurturing these emerging scholars, we are building a strong foundation for future breakthroughs.

My conviction is that research provides the essential evidence base needed to respond effectively to the burdens of SCD care and treatment. Through this groundbreaking study, we aim to illuminate the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland, offering insights that can drive policy changes and improve care practices. By highlighting these lived experiences, we seek to inform and inspire actions that will alleviate the challenges faced by those with SCD and their families.

This journey has been marked by both profound sorrow and unwavering hope. It is my deepest hope that this research will contribute to meaningful change, bringing us closer to a world where individuals with SCD receive the compassionate, comprehensive care they deserve. This work is dedicated to all those who live with SCD and to the memory of my beloved daughter and Queen warrior, Reme, whose spirit continues to inspire and guide me - and everyone else impacted by her short life with us.

Acknowledgements

This research project, “Daily Living Experiences of People Living with Sickle Cell in Ireland: Impact on Education and Employment,” would not have been possible without the support and contributions of many individuals and organisations.

First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to the participants of this study. Your willingness to share your personal experiences and challenges has provided invaluable insights into the realities of living with sickle cell disease in Ireland. Your courage and openness are the foundation of this research. I am profoundly grateful to the six research assistants whose dedication and hard work have been instrumental in conducting and analysing the interviews. Your professionalism, background in medicine and healthcare, and commitment to this study ensured that the data collected was thorough and meaningful. Your diverse perspectives and meticulous analyses have significantly enriched the findings of this research.

A special thank you to Dr Marina Everri for your invaluable guidance and support throughout this project. Your expertise and encouragement have been crucial in navigating the complexities of this research. And to Stephen Mc Mahon, we are very grateful for all your support throughout the years, ensuring our voices are heard in the right spaces. I would also like to acknowledge the Sickle Cell Society Ireland for their continuous support and advocacy. SCSi's commitment to improving the lives of individuals with sickle cell disease has been a constant source of inspiration. I would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to Professor Corrina McMahon for her foundational leadership and dedication to the treatment and development of sickle cell care in Ireland over the years. Her unwavering commitment and expertise have significantly improved the lives of many patients and their families. Special thanks to the International Decade for People of African Descent and the Department of Disability, Equality, Inclusion and Youth who have made this research possible through the funding call launched last May.

On a personal note, I want to dedicate this work to my beloved daughter, whose memory drives my unwavering resolve to advocate for better care and support for individuals with sickle cell disease. Losing you has been the most profound pain, yet it has also ignited a deeper commitment to this cause. Lastly, I would like to thank my family and friends for their endless support and understanding, especially during the most challenging times. Your belief in the importance of this research has been a source of strength and motivation.

This study represents a collective effort to bring about positive change and improved care for individuals with sickle cell disease and their families. I am hopeful that our combined efforts will lead to meaningful advancements in treatment and support.

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Chapter

1.0

Introduction

Esther Onolememen

1.1 Background and Context

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is one of the most common genetic disorders worldwide, with a significant prevalence in regions such as sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East, and India (Kanter and Jordan, 2015; Piel et al., 2014; Leleu et al., 2021). It results from a mutation in the haemoglobin gene, leading to the production of abnormal haemoglobin S. Individuals with SCD inherit two copies of the sickle cell gene, one from each parent, resulting in red blood cells that assume a characteristic sickle shape under low oxygen conditions. This abnormality causes the cells to become rigid and sticky, blocking blood flow and leading to severe complications (Swensen et al 2010).

In Ireland, the prevalence of SCD has increased due to rising immigration from high-prevalence regions (McMahon et al. 2001). Despite this, SCD remains relatively understudied in the Irish context, particularly regarding how individuals manage the disease on a day-to-day basis. This lack of research impedes the development of tailored healthcare strategies and support systems necessary to improve the quality of life for affected individuals.

1.2 Introduction

SCD is a severe inherited hemoglobinopathy that follows an autosomal recessive inheritance pattern. To manifest the disease, an individual must inherit a sickle cell gene from both parents; inheriting only one gene results in carrier status. Globally, SCD affected nearly 8 million people in 2021, predominantly impacting individuals in sub-Saharan Africa. However, due to migration and cultural integration, SCD has also become prevalent in European countries, including England and Ireland. Despite its significant presence, there is a notable lack of research on the impact of SCD in Ireland, particularly its influence on the daily living experiences of affected individuals.

SCD is characterised by various complications affecting multiple organ systems, including sickle cell retinopathy, pulmonary hypertension, stroke, and renal dysfunction. Beyond the physical challenges,

individuals with SCD face substantial psychological and social difficulties, such as stigmatisation and its subsequent impact on mental health, education, and employment. This research aims to explore these dimensions, particularly focusing on the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland, thus addressing a critical gap in the existing literature.

1.3 Research Problem

The core problem this research addresses is the lack of comprehensive understanding and documentation of the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland. This gap in knowledge results in insufficient healthcare services, inadequate support systems, and a general lack of awareness about the challenges faced by this population. Without detailed insights into their experiences, it is challenging to develop effective interventions and policies to improve their quality of life.

1.4 Rationale

The need for this research is underscored by the significant prevalence of SCD in Ireland and the evident lack of comprehensive studies addressing the daily living experiences of those affected. The physical complications of SCD, coupled with psychological issues such as depression, anxiety, and social stigma, create a multifaceted challenge for individuals and their families. Moreover, existing barriers to healthcare access, exacerbated by geographical and systemic limitations, further impede the effective management of the disease.

By exploring the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD, this research aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the challenges they face. The insights gained will be instrumental in informing healthcare policies and practices, ensuring that individuals with SCD receive holistic and empathetic care. Additionally, the study's findings highlight areas where targeted interventions can significantly improve the quality of life for individuals living with SCD in Ireland.

1.5 Aims and Research Questions

The main aim of this research was to explore the daily living experiences of people living with sickle cell disease in Ireland, with a particular focus on how their education and employment are impacted. The research questions and objectives considered for this study are as follows:

- 1** What are the daily living experiences of individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland? The objective is to gather in-depth insights into the daily living experiences of people living with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland in order to gain a proper understanding of their identified issues.
- 2** How do physical complications and psychological challenges associated with sickle cell disease (SCD) impact the quality of life of affected individuals? The objective is to identify the physical, psychological, and social challenges faced by individuals with SCD and analyse the impact on their mental health to understand how these challenges affect other areas of their lives, including their education and employment.
- 3** What barriers do individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) face to accessing healthcare services in Ireland? How can healthcare services and social support systems be improved to better support individuals with SCD? The objective is to evaluate the accessibility and quality of healthcare services available to individuals with SCD in Ireland, identify gaps and areas for improvement, and develop a set of recommendations aimed at policymakers, healthcare providers, and support organisations to enhance the support and quality of care for individuals with SCD.

1.6 Definitions of Key Terminologies

- 1 Sickle Cell Disease (SCD):** An inherited hemoglobinopathy characterised by the presence of sickle-shaped red blood cells, which can obstruct blood flow and lead to various complications.
- 2 Hemoglobinopathy:** Is a group of disorders affecting the haemoglobin molecule in red blood cells.
- 3 Autosomal Recessive Inheritance:** A pattern of inheritance where two copies of an abnormal gene must be present for the disease or trait to develop.
- 4 Vaso-Occlusive Crises (VOC):** Acute pain episodes in individuals with SCD, caused by the blockage of blood vessels by sickled cells.
- 5 Stigmatisation:** The act of treating someone negatively based on a distinguishing characteristic or condition, leading to social disapproval and discrimination.
- 6 Psychosocial Impact:** The effect of social factors and individual thought and behaviour on a person's mental health and well-being.
- 7 Patient-centred care:** Is healthcare that is respectful of and responsive to individual patient preferences, needs, and values.

1.7 Structure of the Research

This research is organised into seven chapters, each focusing on a different aspect of the study, to ensure a comprehensive exploration of the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland.

Chapter 1: Introduction sets the stage for the research by providing an overview of sickle cell disease, highlighting the importance of the study, and outlining the research aims, objectives, questions, and rationale. It introduces the research problem and defines key terminologies used throughout the study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review delves into existing literature on SCD, offering a detailed analysis of the global and local prevalence of the disease. This chapter discusses the physical, psychological, and social challenges associated with SCD and identifies gaps in the existing research, particularly within the context of Ireland. This review sets the foundation for understanding the broader context and the need for this study.

Chapter 3: Methodology describes the research design and approach, explaining the qualitative methods employed to gather data. It outlines the criteria for participant selection, data collection, and analysis procedures and discusses ethical considerations to ensure the study's integrity and adherence to research standards.

Chapter 4: Results presents the findings from the research, using thematic analysis to explore the data collected from participants. This chapter provides key insights into the daily living experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland, highlighting common themes and significant patterns that emerged from the data.

Chapter 5: Discussion interprets the research findings, comparing them with existing literature, and discussing how the findings address the research questions. This chapter also explores the implications of the findings for healthcare policy and practice, emphasising the need for patient-centred care and support tailored to the unique challenges faced by individuals with SCD.

Chapter 6: Recommendations offers practical recommendations for improving the quality of life for individuals with SCD. It provides suggestions for healthcare providers, policymakers, and support organisations, aiming to enhance the support and care available to those affected by SCD. The recommendations are grounded in the research findings and are intended to inform future interventions and policies.

Chapter 7: Conclusion summarises the key findings of the research, reflects on the research process and its contributions, and offers final thoughts on the significance of addressing the needs of individuals with SCD in Ireland. This chapter underscores the importance of continued research and advocacy to improve the lives of those living with SCD.

Chapter
2.0
Literature
Review

Deborah Onolememen,
Lauryn Akeme and Esther
Onolememen

2.1 Introduction

SCD is a common and severe inherited hemoglobinopathy in many parts of the world. The genetic inheritance of SCD adheres to an autosomal recessive pattern, meaning both parents must pass on a sickle cell gene and then a child has a one in four chance of having the SCD condition. Inheriting only one gene from a parent, results in a person having carrier status or carrying the sickle cell gene (Swensen et al 2010). Globally, SCD impacts almost 8 million people (Thomson et al. 2023) but it primarily affects people in sub-Saharan Africa and India (Piel et al. 2014). Due to globalisation, cultural integration and migration SCD is now prevalent in European countries also presenting itself as a global health disparity (Kanter and Jordan, 2015; Piel et al., 2014; Leleu et al., 2021). To illustrate, SCD is one of the most common genetic conditions in England, with a high birth incidence and population of around 15,000 (Keane and Defoe, 2016; Dormandy et al. 2018). Due to medical advances, screening services, diagnostics and intervention with therapeutics and specialised care, SCD is now a chronic condition in most high-income countries like England and the United States (US). Yet, the emergence of SCD in Ireland only gained prominence in the early 2000s, primarily impacting individuals of Nigerian descent, with subsequent cases observed among people descending from Angola and Congo (McMahon et al. 2001). Despite the prevalence of SCD within these communities, as of 2024, there remains a lack of published research both quantifying the extent of its impact and also qualifying how people live with this condition in Ireland, thereby highlighting significant gaps in the existing literature as well as illustrating neglect.

SCD gets its name from the sickle shape that affects red blood cells that deliver oxygen across the body. When those red blood cells become blocked they can cause pain and affect the organs of the body due to lack of oxygen, when this pain is very severe it is termed a crisis. As a systemic multi-organ disease, SCD can also manifest itself in a variety of ways and this changes across the life-course and depending on what type of SCD a person has. There is a mild version HbSC and a more severe version HbSS but no two individuals

are affected in the same way. Generally speaking, it can be observed in multiple organ systems culminating in one or a plethora of complications such as SCD retinopathy, pulmonary hypertension, cardiovascular abnormalities, swelling of the spleen, stroke and renal dysfunction (Fitzhugh et al., 2010; Osunkwo et al, 2021). In addition to the multitude of medical complexities and severe pain observed in SCD, the stigmatisation of the condition and disbelief of pain adds a psychological component to its suffering (Jenerette and Brewser, 2011; Pecker and Darbari, 2019). Leger et al. (2018) suggests that stigma, stemming from factors such as race, family, friendships, or quality of care received, plays a significant role. The social implications of this stigmatisation are noteworthy, as they are believed to exacerbate SCD pain episodes by reducing a patient's inclination to seek analgesic treatment (Leger et al. 2018).

Furthermore, the chronicity and uncertainty of SCD correlates with its influence on education and employment. Some people report heightened absenteeism in educational and employment settings, subsequently impeding career advancement and educational progression (Osunkwo et al., 2022). Research outlines that chronic health conditions impact mental health, extending beyond mere physical discomfort (Huang et al., 2023). SCD in particular, may co-exist with other physical and mental health conditions, such as with anxiety and depression. The physical and psychological complications of SCD play a role in influencing an individual's daily living experiences, that is to say, stressful conditions can lead to more crisis for patients. This research study attempts to highlight the various features which impact the daily living experiences of SCD.

2.2 Sickle Cell Impact on Health, Complications and Access to Care

As stated above, the presence of abnormal haemoglobin in SCD frequently precipitates acute episodes of pain, commonly referred to as vaso-occlusive crises (VOC) or sickle cell

crises. This occurs when the sickled cells aggregate, often leading to clot formation and subsequent occlusion of vessels (Ballas, 1995). The complications of a sickle cell crisis can be severe, often including the likes of acute chest pain, gallstones, avascular necrosis, sepsis, cardiomegaly and many more (Bailey et al., 2020). Studies conducted by Rizio et al. outlined that most patients experienced over four VOC events, many of which were treated in the hospital. A significant portion of hospital utilisations among individuals with SCD are accounted for by visits to the emergency department (ED) and hospital admissions for treatment (Brousseau et al., 2010). ED visits are particularly characterised by a level of high urgency for SCD patients (Bundy et al., 2011). A US-based study conducted by Brousseau et al. (2010) underscored the importance of complications linked to SCD, emphasising that the ability to reduce sickle cell crises may lower the risk of organ damage.

Given that the ED admission frequently serves as the initial point of contact in hospitals for patients encountering pain or complications, it is imperative to guarantee that the care provided is patient-centred, tailored to each individuals' needs, and comprehensive. This approach is vital for reducing complications associated with SCD (Benjamin et al., 2000; Brousseau et al., 2010). Benjamin et al. (2000) demonstrated that prompt and efficient action in healthcare facilities, during a crisis, reduced the risk of hospitalisations in SCD. Patient-centred care is indispensable for ensuring the delivery of quality healthcare especially at times of vulnerability (Inusa et al., 2018). Barriers to healthcare, however, can impede the quality of care received by patients. A study conducted in emergency care settings in Ireland provided insight into the experiences of a variety of patients in the ED (Swalmeh et al., 2018). Participants voiced their frustration over prolonged waits, inadequate communication from healthcare staff, unforeseen delays, and busy nature of the ED. Such issues frequently act as obstacles to delivering optimal and satisfactory patient care. The complex interplay between the racial dynamics of SCD and its prevalence in marginalised communities, coupled with the inherent over-burden of emergency departments, exacerbates the challenge of delivering adequate care. Consequently, stigmatising stereotypes surrounding SCD persist, impeding access to healthcare for affected

individuals. (Bundy et al., 2011; Childerhose et al., 2024). Literature outlines that stigma-related obstacles to accessing care often result in delayed treatment during sickle cell crises, prolonged waiting times, reluctance to seek treatment, heightened risk of future hospitalisations, or apprehension about returning to the ED (Rizio et al., 2020; Abdallah et al., 2020). In a study published by Childerhose et al. (2024), patients reported feeling hesitant to seek treatment amid crises as they were fearful of being referred to as "drug seeking". Bundy et al. (2011) invalidated the idea that individuals with SCD relied excessively on medication, given that their hospital utilisation rates were not disproportionately high. This undermines stereotypes that depict them solely as seeking medication.

Location may serve as another barrier to timely and equitable care for patients with SCD in Ireland. Although not extensively researched in Ireland, studies from other regions have highlighted that patients in rural areas often encounter more obstacles to accessing care compared to their urban counterparts (Buchanan et al., 2006; Smeltzer et al., 2016). Smeltzer et al. (2016) reported that patients living further from specialised care centres had decreased hospitalisations, possibly suggesting distance is a factor in the frequency of hospital utilisations.

According to the Health Service Executive's (HSE) clinical strategy and programmes division for non-malignant haematological diseases (accessed April 19th 2024), specialised treatment for SCD is primarily available in Dublin and Cork for both paediatric and adult patients. However, in Galway, the focus is predominantly on providing care for adults with limited paediatric and established transition services into adult care. Although the implications of the centralisation of SCD care in Ireland have not been studied, Houwing et al. (2021) carried out research based in the Netherlands and they revealed that families were faced with coping with travel expenses due to the distances of the hospitals specialising in SCD care. Interestingly, Houwing et al. (2021) highlighted that healthcare workers specialised in treating SCD reported that many general practitioners (GPs) had very limited knowledge of SCD. Similarly, Keane and Defoe (2016) explained that despite the challenges and limitations mothers faced in the UK with transportation, they often chose to visit hospitals over GPs, as they felt GPs were not always able to offer

the detailed assistance or explanations needed for their children's conditions.

Limited awareness of SCD frequently resulted in either increased referral rates or, alternatively, the overlooking of potentially life-threatening complications. This oversight sometimes led to Intensive Care Unit (ICU) admissions, highlighting the critical nature of the issue (Houwing et al., 2021). When considering the broader implications of SCD, there is a critical link between the lack of GP awareness and general awareness. Two studies carried out by Al Jubri et al. (2012) based in London, outlined many patients did not utilise their GPs for various reasons; lack of rapport, less comprehensive knowledge of the condition or poor communication. The participants felt as though GPs could have an imperative role in the management of SCD (Al Jubri et al., 2012). Whilst specialised centres often possess a deep understanding of patient care, local care facilities and GPs may not have as thorough knowledge of the condition as stated in Houwing et al. (2021). Moreover, Childerhose et al. (2024) investigated the experiences of patients in emergency departments, revealing that some healthcare staff were not only unfamiliar with SCD but, in some cases, had never even heard of it. In a study from the US, 56% of SCD patients attributed a lack of knowledge or training as a barrier to accessing healthcare (Phillips et al., 2022). Consequently, patients disclosed this lack of awareness bred less empathy, misunderstandings of SCD, and unwillingness to build rapport and attentively listen to patient concerns. Although numerous barriers to care have been identified globally, there is a notable gap in research specifically related to SCD in Ireland.

2.3 Sickle Cell and Psychosocial Impact

The interplay between psychological disorders and somatic illnesses have been widely identified and acknowledged throughout literature (Tylee et al., 2005; Chaturvedi, 2013). Studies have demonstrated the bidirectional relationship between psychological disorders such as pain in SCD and depression (Harris et al., 2023; Onyeaka et al., 2019) individuals with SCD

related their chronic symptoms to have a negative impact on their emotional well-being (Osunkwo et al., 2021) However, the association between depression and pain is not the sole contributing factor in the psychosocial implications of SCD, there are a number of socio-cultural and psychological factors which negatively impact the lives of individuals with SCD, such as poor pain management, negative patient experiences, negative societal perceptions and stigmatisation, bullying and poor overall understanding and awareness of SCD throughout communities. (Clayton-Jones et al., 2019; Salih, 2019). Ola et al (2016) found that the link between depression and SCD was linked to the stigma of the condition, and correlation also to lack of treatment and the impacts of racism in healthcare.

Individuals with SCD are at high risk for developing depression due to disease severity, prolonged hospital admission and stay and inadequate acute care treatment (Wilson, 2023). Existing literature has highlighted the irrefutable evidence that suggests SCD is majorly associated with depression or depressive symptoms as well as other physiological disorders (Doglioni et al., 2021). Hasan et al (2003) conducted a study in the United States assessing depression in 50 individuals with SCD, using the Beck Depression Inventory and found that over one-third of the participants had depression. Furthermore, in another study conducted in the US by Adam et al. (2017), it was found that the prevalence of depression in SCD patients was 5 times higher than general populations. Similar to this, a Nigerian study showed that nearly half of the adults and adolescents expressed they had experienced depressive feelings and just under 10% expressed feelings of self-hatred (Anie et al., 2010). Salih (2019) reported 45.8% of study participants in Sudan suffered from depressive symptoms while 29% suffered from depression alone. Evidence suggests that a large proportion of individuals with SCD suffer from poor psychosocial well-being or will develop psychological conditions or mental health disorders. A significant factor contributing to the poor psychosocial well-being of individuals with SCD is als bullying and problematic peer relationships experienced from childhood through to adulthood (Anie et al., 2010; Salih, 2019), as well as racism too (Ola et al 2016).

Studies have supported the idea that societies' negative ideas and perceptions have a negative psychosocial impact on people with SCD. In a study conducted in Nigeria, using a self-complete questionnaire, it was found that over 60% of adults and adolescents had reported they felt the general public held a negative societal attitude and less than one-third reported experiencing teasing or bullying throughout their education and employment due to SCD (Anie et al., 2010). Similarly, in a cross-sectional observational study conducted in Sudan, the study reported that among 107 participants, 29% suffered from teasing by their teachers, classmates and communities (Salih, 2019). In another study conducted in Nigeria, Ola et al (2016) reported in their study that participants had negative discriminatory remarks directed at them throughout their life from family members, neighbours, school or work colleagues and strangers. Participants also reported disapproval and devaluation from significant others which caused a plethora of emerging feelings such as sadness, and helplessness and one participant described feeling "like dying" (Ola et al., 2016). This demonstrated the infiltrative extent of how societal perceptions impacted the well-being of people with SCD. It highlights that the negative psychosocial impact of SCD is not solely related to the complications of the disease, but the negative implications from a societal aspect.

Anxiety is another prominent feature in the lives of people with SCD, this has been related to frequent hospitalisations, suboptimal treatment of acute pain, as well as the unpredictability and inconsistencies in the attitudes of healthcare responders. While medical complications limit people living with SCD, the active prevention of crises and complications serves as a factor inducing anxiety and precipitating low psychosocial mood within the sickle cell community.

Hospitalisations are known to be a distressing experience for people with SCD, in a study by Childerhose et al. (2024), exploring the distressing experiences of persons with SCD, they found that patients characterised their experiences in acute care settings as anger, frustration, resentment, bewilderment and resignation. The attitudes of healthcare providers play as a huge factor in how effectively and efficiently a patient is managed.

Negative attitudes towards SCD patients is one of the prominent and most detrimental factors leading to barriers to adequate care and anxiety-inducing episodes in patients with SCD. In contrast to the study conducted by Childerhose (2024), providing a distressing patient perspective, Stewart et al. (2021) conducted a cross-national study of provider attitudes regarding pain management in SCD, it was found that providers had expressed strained relationships with patients and described patients to be defensive, angry and frustrated, while other providers went to the extent of describing communications as verbally abusive. This study highlighted that the undertreatment of pain resulted in strained relationships between healthcare providers and their patients (Stewart et al, 2021). From this, we can underscore the negative emotions experienced by patients with SCD seeking out medical care, and the poor translation of this from a provider's perspective.

Freirmuth et al. (2014) and Royal et al. (2011) showed that patients frequently reported negative attitudes and greater frustration from healthcare providers when presenting with pain events. The negative impact of these encounters may result in future apprehensions and hostility towards medical providers. Another significant finding in Friermuths study was that nurses reported higher estimates of opioid addictions among SCD patients (Freirmuth et al., 2014). Patients with SCD presenting to healthcare facilities for management of their pain are globally stigmatised as exhibiting drug-seeking behaviours, studies have shown that patients with SCD have been negatively perceived to have opioid addictions. In a study conducted by Royal et al (2011), it was shown that one-fifth of the participants felt that they were generally perceived and treated as drug addicts by healthcare providers.

This unfair stigmatisation can be detrimental to the physical and emotional health of SCD patients. These provider attitudes ultimately endanger patients with SCD, as they have a preconceived perception of the pain experienced by sickle cell patients and how to manage their pain. By holding this perception, it can lead to inaccurate treatment in acute settings which may alter the course of a patient's crises. This highlights the cross-cultural gaps in how people

experience and express pain. The person with sickle cell hardly wins, unless they either become aggressive or docile according to Berghs et al (2022).

This stigmatisation shows that healthcare providers do not believe or are willing to accept the level of pain that SCD individuals suffer, as they attribute it to an addiction with no substantial evidence that would suggest this other than their own perceptions (Ezenwa et al., 2016). This creates inevitable mistrust between healthcare providers and patients which further strain the relationship (Haywood et al, 2010). Patients have associated this unfair stigmatisation with the colour of their skin, emphasis has been made on the relationship between being described as “drug-seeking” and Black patients (Royal et al, 2011). Healthcare providers are aware that pain is subjective, hence the availability of widely known and validated pain assessment tools being key in acute care settings, these tools become pointless and ineffective in circumstances where healthcare providers show prejudice and reluctance when managing pain (Stewart et al., 2021).

Given the existing data surrounding the relationship between SCD patients and healthcare providers during pain episodes, the lack of understanding and complexities that follow pain assessment and treatment often lead to an understandable level of frustration and anger amongst these patients. There are nuanced and complex perspectives involved in exploring and understanding how individuals with SCD suffer from poor psychological well-being. Extensive literature, across many borders have shown that the specific drivers and factors of stigmatisation and negative psychosocial behaviours may vary across different cultural and societal contexts, the way in which these issues manifest can often be quite similar and provide a consistency in the existing data despite the variations in study types, participants, cultural backgrounds and geographical locations. Through extensively reviewing the available literature concerning Psychosocial implications of SCD, there was a large concentration of Studies done within West Africa and the USA. However, there remains an evident lack of research within Ireland and the rest of the European countries.

2.4 Sickle Cell and Impact on Family

Aside from its considerable mental and physical effects, SCD also impacts external aspects of life, notably affecting interpersonal relationships and having the capacity to alter the family dynamics. The family impact of the conditions has been previously described by some families as burdensome, stressful and demanding (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000). The unpredictable nature of acute crises in SCD often leaves families in a state of anxious anticipation, worrying when the next episode might occur (Bailey et al., 2020; Blake et al., 2018). Parents also voiced concerns about their child’s academic progress, fearing that frequent absences from school due to their condition might hinder their ability to achieve their full potential (Keane and Defoe, 2016). In research published by Karadağ et al. (2018) all research participants expressed fears of losing their child due to SCD. Furthermore, Atkin and Ahmad (2000) denoted that parents of children with the condition reported an intense focus on their child, particularly during health crises, leading them to feel as if their personal lives were on hold. Approximately 70% of mothers indicated that their hyperfixation of their child with SCD significantly limited the time available for their spouses and similarly restricted the attention they could give to their other children (Karadağ et al. 2018). Despite the strain experienced by families with SCD affiliations, parents affectionately labelled their children as courageous, often referring to them as ‘sickle cell warriors,’ expressing pride in their resilience against the challenges they face (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000).

Remarkably however, while the impact of SCD affects entire families, the majority of the caregiving burden disproportionately falls on the mothers (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000; Karadağ et al., 2018); Ünal et al., 2011). Maternal caregivers frequently reported frustration stemming from a lack of support from paternal spouses, often leading to tensions with their mothers-in-law (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000). The increased caregiving burden on mothers has possibly been linked to a higher risk of developing psychiatric conditions, namely major depressive disorder and obsessive-compulsive disorder, moreover, this was not noted in any paternal figures (Ünal et al., 2011).

Families managing SCD may face significant financial challenges. Beyond the costs of medications and hospital visits, there are also environmental impacts on crisis for patients with sickle cell. The need to maintain warm indoor temperatures significantly increases financial outlays for families (Keane and Defoe, 2016). Temperature changes, especially cold weather, can trigger SCD crises by increasing pain sensitivity (Brandow et al. 2019). This heightened sensitivity necessitates continuous heating, as recommended by specialists to manage VOCs (Harley, 2013). Consequently, the constant use of heating systems leads to increased household expenses (Keane and Defoe, 2016) and there is a correlation to socio-economic class and inequality.

Families often face additional levels of stress due to delayed diagnosis and lack of medical knowledge of their children's condition (Witt et al., 2023). Caprini and Motta (2021) underlined that 96% of participants were unaware that the sickle cell trait (SCT) existed within their family lineage, and 92% were unaware that the condition was genetic. Beyond this, over 60% of the respondents became aware that their child had SCD between the ages 1 and 5 when the first symptoms, for instance, of swelling of hands and feet became apparent. Keane and Defoe's (2016) study in the UK highlights that the confirmation of their child's SCD often left mothers feeling both shocked and devastated, some mothers even reported suicidal ideations and unwillingness to cope with the guilt they felt from "giving" the condition to their child.

The lack of awareness about the SCT in families might be attributed to the stigmatisation associated with the condition, which is often regarded as a "family secret." This stigma likely leads to minimal discussion and limited sharing of information about the condition within and beyond the family (Keane and Defoe, 2016; Leger et al., 2018). The absence of awareness or open dialogue within families regarding SCT compelled women living with SCD to adopt a more vigilant approach to dating (Ross, 2015). Frequently, they sought information about their partners' genotype or advocated for genetic testing. In expressing their concerns, these women emphasised their determination not to replicate their parents' oversights and perceived their mothers as insufficiently assertive in persuading their fathers to undergo genotype

testing. The substantial challenges faced by caregivers highlight the broader need for better recognition of the sickle cell trait within families, compounded by difficulties in obtaining testing and a widespread lack of awareness about the condition itself

2.5 Sickle Cell and Impact on Education

Studies dating back as far as 30 years have explored and proven that SCD is associated with poor school performance and poor educational attainment patterns. Fowler (1988) compared neuropsychological results and academic functioning amongst children with SCD and found they scored significantly low results. In a comparative study between children with SCD, and their healthy siblings, it was demonstrated that children with SCD had lower academic achievements in comparison to their unaffected siblings, with over 50% more school absences than that of their siblings. They found that the crises experienced by these children were associated with frequent hospitalisations, interruptions of child activities, and loss of school time (Ogunfowora et al., 2005). These results were substantiated by future studies in this area of research, such as more recent studies conducted by Heitzer (2021) in the US, and Alhazmi et al. (2022) in Saudi Arabia, which evaluated the impact of SCD on academic performance. Heitzer (2021) found that the academic performance of students with SCD was negatively affected compared to healthy individuals. Alhazmi et al. (2022) found that students with SCD demonstrated notable academic difficulties. Despite the years of evidence, there is a current lack of school performance intervention for people living with SCD. Heitzer (2021) and Alhazmi (2022) among other studies have suggested further national studies on larger populations and educational programs to enhance academic performance.

Thomas and Taylor (2003) recognised and suggested 4 domains to education in individuals with SCD: The physical domain, psychological domain, social relationships and environment. Literature in the past 2 decades have explored these domains through extensive qualitative research.

In a qualitative UK study exploring the experiences of young people with SCD in school, it was found that participants described negative school experiences such as classroom requests pertaining to health maintenance (frequent hydrating, trips to the toilet and limiting physical activity) as disruptive (Dyson et al., 2012). In another study conducted in the UK, Dyson et al. (2010) demonstrated that over three quarters of the young people in their study reported experiencing at least one type of negative school experience such as “prevented from using the toilet, prevented from drinking water, made to do unsuitable exercise or called lazy when tired”. The description of being “lazy” is based on the lack of knowledge of teachers regarding SCD and how anaemia subsequently results in fatigue. Guidelines were published by Dyson (2012) which recommended school policies to improve the school experience of young people with SCD. These policies equip teachers to create an inclusive atmosphere with further knowledge of SCD and allowance of reasonable adjustments for students with SCD and all students (e.g water breaks are not disruptive, people with SCD require frequent hydration to prevent crises from occurring)

As a consequence of these collective factors, school absences are a prominent feature in the lives of young people with SCD (Schwartz et al., 2009; Dyson et al., 2010). These existing data indicate the necessity of educating teachers and introducing school programs that allow for these students to make up for absences and gain support from their teachers in furthering their education despite obstacles faced (Dyson et al., 2013:2). Another major factor contributing to the unique educational experience of young people with SCD is the neurocognitive aspect. It is widely recognised that SCD is associated with major complications involving major blood vessels of the central nervous system, leading to stroke as a result of stenosis and subsequent occlusion of large intracranial arteries (Light et al. 2023). In a systematic review, Abdi et al (2023) found that children with SCD showed poor cognition compared to controls which related to the presence of overt stroke or silent cerebral infarctions. Stroke and its sequelae are known to directly impact school performance and educational patterns based primarily on impaired neuropsychological function and secondarily on school absences due to hospitalisation and rehabilitation (Day, 2006).

Stroke in children with SCD is commonly known as ‘micro-infarction’ or ‘silent-infarction’. Stroke is a relatively common complication amongst younger individuals with SCD, however, the presentation may differ among patients, and the lack of clinical manifestation of silent strokes leads to the delayed or undetected intervention of neuropsychological impairment which may be contributing to poor academic performance. According to the American Heart Association (Talahma et al., 2014), children with sickle cell disease are 200 to 400 times more likely to suffer a stroke compared to children without the condition, with the highest incidence occurring during the middle of a child’s first decade of life. This period of a child’s life is integral to the development of their academic performance. In a retrospective study, Babeer et al. (2023), in Saudi Arabia, found the prevalence of stroke among children with SCD to be 16%. In the United States, Crosby et al. (2015) showed that 40% of the participants in their study reported repeating a grade at some point in their school career and 37% of participants reported receiving special education services. Based on existing data, there seems to be a directly proportional relationship between disease severity, medical complications, and school absences, which collectively impact school performance and educational attainment patterns.

The combination of these factors leads to poor educational attainment such as lower grades, repeating the school year, and inadequate preparation for college application. Collectively, these factors can negatively impact further education and as a result, impact employment. Reviewing previous and current literature on the impact of sickle cell disease on education, has shown that while we can acknowledge the many factors that contribute to poor academic performance, many of these factors display a casual relationship. Whilst disability legislation makes provision in relation to a person with disability to mean “a substantial restriction in the capacity of the person to carry on a profession, business or occupation in the State or to participate in social or cultural life in the State by reason of an enduring physical, sensory, mental health or intellectual impairment.” (Irish Statue Book, 2005), Ireland still has a gap in embracing the disability policies that ensures reasonable adjustments are made to recognise the disease severity between

medical complications arising from sickle cell and school absences and impact on educational and life cycle attainment for patients.

2.6 Sickle Cell and Impact on Employment

It is recognised that people with SCD are employed in a wide variety of formal professions such as teachers, nurses, pharmacists and bank clerks (Dyson and Barghs, 2020). However, it is important to acknowledge the varied experiences in terms of workplace discrimination, poor understanding from employers and colleagues and crises' resulting in absenteeism. A prominent dilemma across literature pertains to individuals disclosing their condition to employers and the possible implications of this disclosure. Disclosure is not necessary at interviews and Dyson and Berghs (2020) suggested that disclosure to HR or OH after employment may be beneficial to accommodate their health needs and make workplace adjustments as per disability legislation. Berghs (2010) found that many people with SCD did not fully understand their rights and legislation around workplace accommodations, and struggled with issues like if and when they should disclose their condition to employers. Another aspect to this dilemma, involves the possibility of employers deciding not to go through with employment due to anticipating irregular attendance or limitations to work abilities (Franklin and Atkin, 1986). In a study conducted nearly 40 years ago, it was found that major employers in the UK west midlands lacked a comprehensive understanding of SCD (Franklin et al., 1986). This remains a current problem that is still faced worldwide. People with visible manifestations of SCD had experienced disablism in employment such as not being invited for interviews, a lack of workplace accommodation, explicit hostility to their disability and loss of employment (Dyson and Berghs 2020). Berghs (2021) discussed the aspect of invisible disability in the UK, one participant in their study described colleagues considering them as "undeserving of adjustments" owing to the fact that they could not see how ill they were, therefore judging them as "able". Another participant described how a manager was not attentive

to reasonable adjustments needed (Berghs et al. 2021) and employers often disregard the necessary self-care required by workers with SCD, prioritising productivity over their health needs.. Dyson et al. (2021) stated that "disabled black workers with SCD face a daunting range of challenges in negotiating their health in relation to employment."

Work absences play a significant role in how SCD impacts employment. It has been studied widely across literature conducted through multiple countries. The consistency in data regarding work absences in SCD underscore the prevalent problem faced by individuals with SCD. In a US cohort of 74 sickle cell disease (SCD) patients, 51 patients had continuous employment history greater than 12 months. Of these, 39 (76.47%) were unemployed. The majority of patients (90.20%) were hospitalised at least once, and 16 patients (31.37%) were hospitalised more than 5 times during the previous 12 months (Idowu et al., 2018). Similarly, Gordon et al (2024) conducted a study in the US that showed a total of 22.1% reported missing 5 or more days of work in the last year due to hospitalisations and twice as many adults with SCD missed 10 or more days compared with caregivers of children (21.3% vs 10.7%, respectively). Many individuals with SCD are required to develop coping mechanisms and strategies in order to participate in employment and various forms of work, Dyson and Berghs (2020) also found that there was a significant number of participants that were self-employed in the UK often because it allows them to manage their time and energy levels. This finding indicates individuals with SCD may choose this route of self-employment to have the ability to control their work environment and adjust their work to their health requirements.

While there remains a significant challenge in managing SCD health related complications and absenteeism in work, individuals living with SCD often face problems with securing and maintaining employment. In the UK, Franklin and Atkin (1986) found that out of 13 patients, 8 had lost at least one job because of sickle-cell disease and had usually suffered repeated brief absences from work because of painful crises. Individuals with SCD often face difficulties with securing and maintaining employment (Thomas and Taylor, 2003). Through qualitatively interviewing 20 individuals with SCD, researchers

found that participants faced considerable barriers to accessing and retaining employment due to ableist attitudes and practices, despite the relatively simple and inexpensive accommodations needed (Berghs et al., 2021). In a study conducted in the USA consisting of 244 participants (adults and caregivers of children with SCD). Adults had a much higher rate of employment loss in the last 5 years than caregivers of children with SCD 11.9% vs. 6.7%, respectively (Gordon et al., 2024).

A multi-country, cross-sectional study using a survey was conducted across 11 high-income (HI) countries (Bahrain, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Oman, Panama, Saudi Arabia, USA, UK) and 5 low to middle income (LMI) countries (Brazil, Ghana, India, Nigeria and Lebanon) with a total of 2145 participants. Of the 572 working patients had missed an average of 7 hours of work because of SCD in the 7 days before the survey completion. 53% reported a reduction in work hours due to SCD and 60% of HI and 48% of LMI countries thought that their income would be higher if they did not have SCD (Osunkwo et al., 2021). Osunkwo et al (2022) conducted a similar study a year later with the same methodology, with study groups including the USA (384 patients), 11 High-income countries (HI): 820 patients, 5 Low- to middle-income (LMI) countries: 941 patients. A higher proportion of patients in the US group strongly agreed that SCD had prevented them from attending work, impaired their ability to keep a job, prevented them from finding a suitable job, and caused them to be turned down at job interviews compared with the HI and LMI groups. HI and LMI groups felt they were prevented from being promoted at work, HI groups felt that SCD limited them to certain careers and prevented them from progressing further in their career compared with LMI group (Osunkwo et al. 2022).

Studies have suggested that developing interventions and programs to improve job accommodation for SCD patients may decrease hospitalisation and related healthcare costs. Unemployed SCD patients have a significantly higher rate of hospitalisation for pain crises when compared with employed SCD patients. (Idowu et al. 2018; Dyson et al., 2021). Throughout literature, it appears that the US made up a large amount of the existing data surrounding studies pertaining to how SCD impacts employment, although there have been

studies conducted in the UK, it is a small quantity in comparison to the available research surrounding other well known diseases. We found that there was an overall lack of research within Ireland, further highlighting the pressing demand for increased interest and focus within this domain of research.

2.7 Conclusion

The literature review highlights the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), emphasising the significant physical, psychological, and social burdens associated with the condition. SCD is characterised by severe health complications, including vaso-occlusive crises, which contribute to substantial morbidity and mortality. The psychological impact, marked by high rates of depression and anxiety, is exacerbated by social stigma and inadequate healthcare support.

Despite the global prevalence of SCD, research within the Irish context is notably limited. This gap underscores the necessity for more localised studies to inform healthcare policies and practices tailored to the unique needs of individuals with SCD in Ireland. The review identifies critical areas where further research is essential, particularly in understanding the daily living experiences of those affected and the barriers they face in accessing healthcare and support services.

The interplay between physical health, mental well-being, and social factors is evident, necessitating a holistic approach to managing SCD. Effective interventions must address not only the medical aspects but also the psychological and social dimensions of the disease. Improved awareness and education among healthcare providers and the general public are crucial in reducing stigma and enhancing support for individuals with SCD.

In summary, the literature review underscores the urgent need for comprehensive research and targeted interventions to improve the quality of life for individuals with SCD. By addressing the gaps in understanding and support, we can move towards more effective management and care for this vulnerable population in Ireland.

Chapter
3.0
Methodology

**Doris Obialor, Sinead Ryan,
Margaret Akano and
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3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the research design, sampling strategy, recruitment process, data collection methods, data analysis techniques, data management practices, and ethical considerations employed in this study. The primary objective of this research was to explore the lived experiences of individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland, focusing on how the condition impacts their education and employment trajectories. Given the qualitative nature of this study, a robust and systematic approach was necessary to ensure the collection of rich, detailed data that accurately reflects participants' personal experiences. This chapter details the comprehensive processes undertaken to achieve this goal, providing transparency and rigour to the research methodology. Through a combination of purposive sampling, semi-structured in depth interviews, and reflexive thematic analysis, this study aimed to fill a critical gap in the existing literature on sickle cell disease within the Irish context. The following sections provide an in-depth account of the methods and procedures used to conduct this research, highlighting the careful planning and ethical considerations that guided each step of the study.

3.2 Reflexivity and Positionality of Researchers

"...Compiling, writing, and editing this research has been a profoundly reflective journey for me, requiring significant strength to step back from direct involvement. I recognized the importance of positioning myself objectively, given my deep personal immersion in this subject matter. To ensure the integrity of the study, I trained and supervised six research assistants, a number that some might consider excessive for a small sample size. However, this approach was deliberate and strategic.

The involvement of multiple researchers minimised bias, as each brought a fresh perspective and independent analysis to the data. This diverse team of young researchers, equipped with backgrounds as both students of medicine and health science and professionals working within the healthcare field, ensured a rigorous and comprehensive approach to data collection and analysis.

Their expertise and commitment to the project reinforced the study's validity and richness.

This process was particularly meaningful to me, given my personal journey with sickle cell disease, having two children affected by it. Last year, I experienced an indescribable personal tragedy when I lost one of my children to this disease. This loss has been a catalyst, sparking an even greater need within me to pursue further evidence-based knowledge to improve care for patients and their families. The memory of my child propels me forward, instilling in me an unyielding zeal to advocate for advancements in SCD treatment and care.

The debriefing meetings with the young researchers were eye-opening, as I witnessed their surprise and emotional responses to the recurrent themes of struggle, stigma, and inadequate healthcare access faced by families today—issues that were alarmingly similar to those I encountered over two decades ago when my advocacy began. Reflecting on the continuity of these struggles, even after over 16 years since my unpublished Trinity MSW research which laid the foundation for the Sickle Cell Society Ireland, I realised the enduring relevance of my past findings. This acknowledgement was both disheartening and a stark reminder of the persistent gaps in support and awareness. However, it also reinforced the importance of our continued efforts and collaborations with existing organisations, healthcare professionals, and governmental bodies.

Recognising that there is still much work to be done has deepened my resolve. The way forward for families affected by sickle cell disease involves a comprehensive, collaborative approach to ensure they receive the best possible care and support. My experience with this research underscores the critical need for ongoing advocacy, improved healthcare strategies, and heightened public awareness to bring about meaningful change. My child's memory continues to inspire and guide me in this vital work...." (Esther)

"...Our study demonstrated how deeply SCD permeated nearly every aspect of the daily lives of these individuals. Physical health, psychological health, education, career opportunities and personal relationships were consistently affected. It raised the important question of 'how do we measure their quality of life' considering how extensively it was impacted. I was deeply moved by the

adversity each person faced. I found that the interviews and personal stories revealed a domino effect, where each challenge exacerbated the next, creating a complex web of interconnected difficulties. Despite their varied backgrounds, profound patterns of struggle emerged among the individuals. It showed how important it is to prevent such struggles to be potentially faced by other people with SCD. What struck me the most was how resilient each individual was, and how they navigated a life which centred around preventing these complications and almost inevitable challenges. This study not only aimed to raise awareness but also proved to be a significant and invaluable learning experience for me. I gained a newfound understanding of the hidden struggles of those with SCD, offering me a perspective I wouldn't have reached without participating in this study..." (Lauryn).

"...Participating in this study has been such an enlightening and transformative experience for me. Initially, I had approached this study with a combination of both excitement and uncertainty as I had never done a study of this sort before but as we progressed with the study, my understanding of sickle cell and its multilayered impact increased significantly and I found myself progressively appreciating the significance of the research we were conducting especially as in Ireland this is the first study of its kind to date. One of the most significant aspects of this study for me was the opportunity to personally engage with research participants, hearing their accounts of how sickle cell affected their lives and those around them increased my sense of motivation in continuing and completing this research study. Additionally, the outstanding teamwork within the research team was such a great experience to be a part of. I gained such knowledgeable insights into the methodologies and rigorous processes involved in scientific research which I found very helpful when it came to writing the discussion segment of the study. During the writing of the discussion section there were a lot of revelations about the issues within the Irish healthcare system surrounding sickle cell, many things I was unaware of prior to joining this study such as the huge psychological impact of sickle cell which I may have subconsciously been ignorant to due to lack of the of awareness concerning it. Overall, I really enjoyed my experience with participating in this study, it has been such an educational and motivational experience. It has really given me a deeper understanding of sickle cell and

the unique daily living experiences of those living with the disease and has opened my eyes to the immense gaps in the Irish healthcare system. I really do believe this study will be a great reference for education and a remedy for these gaps. Moving forward I endeavour to continue to participate in further studies in order to continue to make a positive impact in healthcare..." (Dr. Ojuka).

"...Being a part of the research team that investigated how sickle cell disease affects the day-to-day lives of those who have the condition in Ireland has been incredibly enlightening. Through the research process, I was able to learn more about the many and complex obstacles that sickle cell patients in a primarily Caucasian population must overcome. The participants' strikingly different accounts of their day-to-day experiences living with SCD were among the things that most surprised me during this process. No two accounts were the same. It has become clear to me after this investigation that the experiences of each individual have been widely influenced by a number of factors, including the severity of their condition, whether they were born in Ireland or not, their age, their level of education or employment status, and whether they are receiving care from an adult healthcare facility or the children's hospital. The amount of praise given to Crumlin Children's Hospital's haematology department also astounded me. My interviewee expressed gratitude to the team for the consistent care and support that he and the other patients receive from every member of staff. He also made it a point to mention that, of all the children's hospitals in the Dublin region, Crumlin is the only one that responds appropriately and offers the most amount of assistance when a sickle cell patient needs emergency care.

Overall, I found this to be a very rewarding and valuable experience. After hearing the inspiring and moving stories of the seven participants who took part in this research project, it is abundantly clear that there is still so much work that needs to be done in Ireland in order to fully and effectively support the thousands of people living with SCD in the country. I am honoured to have been a part of something as important as this project. I truly believe it is going to make a huge difference in the way the government, healthcare facilities, and the general public care for and treat every sickle warrior in Ireland and beyond..." (Margaret).

"...It's been a great experience of working with a team

to create a research framework and follow it through to an article. Ms Esther's teaching was excellent and a huge help. Not only do I feel more knowledgeable on the daily struggles of living with SCD but also that I can now share these experiences in a scholarly manner. This science writing ability will definitely be helpful in my future career as well and is a skill largely ignored in medicine training despite the fact that physicians are expected to lead and conduct research throughout their careers..." (Jess).

"...Reflecting on this research, I observed that sickle cell disease profoundly impacts all aspects of daily life, particularly affecting school attendance and participation and has led to limiting beliefs among many patients regarding their future. The frequent pain crises and hospitalisations disrupt education, leading to significant academic struggles and absenteeism, with one participant facing a crisis during the duration of the study itself.

Yet, despite these challenges, I was deeply moved by the remarkable resilience of the individuals. Many demonstrated a strong resistance to seeking help, showcasing an admirable, though sometimes detrimental, determination to manage their condition independently. This research has deepened my appreciation for their strength and highlighted the need for enhanced support systems for the warriors living with sickle cell.

Researching this topic proved both challenging and enlightening. Connecting with the emotional weight of the patients' challenges was profound, and highlighted the glaring gaps in social support that must be addressed. This also reaffirmed the critical importance of producing patient-centred research in this area to highlight their own lived experiences and needs..." (Sinead).

"...Being part of this research project has been deeply rewarding. My dedication to sickle cell research originates from my medical education at university and is further intensified by my personal experience living with the condition and the heartbreaking loss of my sister to it.

The experiences of sickle cell patients are uniquely profound and, to my knowledge, have not been extensively explored in Ireland. Thus, being involved in conducting this research and having the opportunity to share my passion, knowledge, and skills has been a great honor. During my interview with Jane Doe, her journey with sickle cell, like others', unfolded as a distinctive

narrative. Through her challenges with complications and the impact on her mental well-being, I became more convinced that sickle cell disease defies a uniform description. Each person's journey is profoundly personal and distinct. During the literature review preparation, it became apparent that sickle cell research in Ireland is notably underexplored. There is a pressing need for patient-centered and epidemiological research. Obtaining updated statistics on the number of sickle cell patients in Ireland proved challenging, with the most detailed research paper dating back 23 years. This significant gap in Irish sickle cell research underscores a critical need for further investigation. The participants consistently noted a lack of awareness about sickle cell disease in Ireland, which likely contributes to this research gap.

I am hopeful that this research will shed a unique and new light on the world of sickle cell and that all those living with sickle cell feel empowered as we wedge towards the closure of these research discrepancies..." (Deborah).

3.3 Aim and Research Questions

The main aim of this qualitative research project was to explore the daily living experiences of people living with sickle cell in Ireland with a particular focus on how their education and employment are impacted. The research questions and objectives considered for this study are as follows:

- 1 What are the daily living experiences of individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in Ireland? The objective is to gather in-depth insights into the daily living experiences of people living with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in Ireland in order to gain a proper understanding of their identified issues.
- 2 How do physical complications and psychological challenges associated with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) impact the quality of life of affected individuals? The objective is to identify the physical, psychological, and social challenges faced by individuals with SCD and analyse the impact on their mental health to understand how these challenges affect other areas of their lives, including their education and employment.

-
- 3** What barriers do individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) face in accessing healthcare services in Ireland? And how can healthcare services and social support systems be improved to better support individuals with SCD? The objective is to evaluate the experience of accessibility and quality of healthcare services available to individuals with SCD in Ireland.
 - 4** How can services be improved to support the identified challenges and needs of individuals with SCD in Ireland? The objective here is to identify gaps and areas for improvement and develop a set of recommendations aimed at policymakers, healthcare providers, and support organisations to enhance the support and quality care for individuals with SCD.

- B Focus on Patterns and Themes:** Thematic analysis places significant emphasis on identifying and interpreting themes that emerge from the data. This aligned with our research aim of exploring the personal and subjective experiences of people with sickle cell disease. By focusing on common patterns and themes, the research highlighted the unique ways in which different people experienced and interpreted their condition.
- C Flexibility:** The thematic analysis provides a flexible approach to data analysis that can be adapted to the specific needs and contexts of the research. This flexibility was important in allowing the research to evolve as new themes emerged from the data.

3.4 Research Framework

This research study adopted the thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2019) approach as its guiding framework. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research method used to identify, analyse, and report patterns (themes) within data. It is particularly useful for examining the perspectives of different research participants, highlighting similarities and differences, and generating unanticipated insights.

3.4.1 Reflexive Thematic Analysis Framework

Braun and Clarke (2019) developed key steps to be taken during a thematic analysis which was observed during our process of data analysis:

- A In-depth Understanding:** Reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) is particularly suited for studies where the goal is to gain an in-depth understanding of complex lived experiences. People living with sickle cell disease often face multifaceted challenges that impact various aspects of their daily lives. The reflexive thematic analysis allowed for a thorough exploration of participants' experiences, providing rich, nuanced insights into how they navigate their daily lives with the condition.

3.5 Research Design

This study was conducted using qualitative methodology (Bryman, 2016) to gain nuanced insights into the participants' lived experiences. In-depth one-to-one semi-structured interviews were used to collect data from six participants diagnosed with sickle cell disease living in Ireland, with a specific focus on the impact of the condition on their experience in education and employment. Given the scarcity of research on this life-impacting condition in the Irish context, this study seeks to address a critical gap in understanding the ways that living with SCD impacts individuals throughout their education and employment trajectory (Alston & Bowles, 2003:87-115-6). The qualitative data was flexible and adaptable, which allowed researchers to explore themes (Braun and Clarke, 2019) as they emerged throughout the research. Several qualitative approaches were initially considered to address the study objectives, such as case studies and grounded theory. RTA analysis was ultimately decided as the most suitable to focus on understanding the subjective and personal lived experiences of those with Sickle Cell and it additionally provided nuanced insights into their experiences within education and employment.

3.6 Sampling

The inclusion criteria for participants were adults aged 18 to 30 living with SCD, residing in Ireland, and having pursued some level of education in Ireland. Participants who were hospitalised or receiving acute care during the data collection period were excluded from the study.

3.6.1 Participant Selection

Purposeful sampling was used to recruit 7 participants who have distinct experiences living with sickle cell disease. This small, focused sample size was appropriate for thematic analysis, allowing for a detailed and thorough examination of each participant's narrative to identify individuals with sickle cell disease in Ireland whose education and employment were likely affected by the condition. Recruitment began on January 14, 2024, through engaging and informative posts on various social media platforms detailing the study's purpose,

eligibility requirements, contact information, and a link to the application form.

Potential participants were invited to apply via the link provided. Out of eleven completed applications, seven participants were recruited within the Sickle Cell Society Ireland's National community network. The eligible participants were initially contacted via email by the principal researcher and received information about the research topic and a consent form. All participants completed their consent forms and returned via email to the principal researcher. Contact details for the principal researcher were shared with the participants to allow for any questions. Participants were duly informed by the principal researcher that each participant would be assigned a research assistant. Upon returning the signed consent form, participants' details were shared with the research assistant assigned to conduct respective interviews. Of the seven participants initially recruited, one participant dropped out prior to data collection as she did not feel ready to share her experience after further consideration.

3.6.2. Research Participants' Profile

Pseudonyms	Age	Gender	Education	Occupation	Years living in Ireland
Jane Loe	22	F	Undergraduate studies	Student/unemployed	22 (Born in Ireland)
John Doe	24	M	Masters	Digital media Intern	<2 Years (arrived Ireland at age 22)
Damian	25	F	Undergraduate degree	IT specialist	15 Years (arrived Ireland at age 10)
Israel	19	M	Undergraduate studies	Employed/student	19 years (born in Ireland)
Paul	20	M	Secondary School	Chef	4 (arrived Ireland at age 16)
Tia	21	F	Undergoing Masters program	Social care assistant/student	<1 Year (less than a year in Ireland)

- Of the six participants interviewed, two participants were born in Ireland, while the other four arrived in Ireland at the age of 22, 16, 10 and 1 year respectively.
- Three of the six participants were still students at varying levels of education, one had dropped out of school during his secondary school stage, while the other two had completed their Masters degree and undergraduate degree respectively.
- Two of the six participants were students and employed, while three others were solely in employment and one was both in employment and also a student at the same time.

3.7 Data Collection

Data collection occurred between April 1 and May 15, 2024, using semi-structured in-depth interviews (Bryman, 2016). The interviews were conducted following an interview guide constructed by the principal researcher using the literature review to identify the gaps in existing literature. The challenge here was the sparse literature in Ireland, so literature used for this purpose was mainly derived from the United Kingdom (Dyson et al, 2010; Ola et al, 2016; Dyson and Berghs, 2020; Inusa et al, 2020; Berghs, 2021; Dyson et al., 2021 and the United States (Osunkwo et al, 2022; Osunkwo et al, 2021) respectively. A debriefing meeting was held by the principal researcher to train and brief the research assistants on their interview guides, and the methodological process. Six research assistants, each conducting an interview with one participant, supported the principal researcher. The research assistant 1:1 ratio to the participants was discussed with the participants, and the participants knew about this approach from the start and were happy with it. The differing research assistants all had a different interview and only the principal researcher had access to the full name of lists of the participants. The six research assistants were necessary to understand the full range of issues for a pilot study and the principal researcher needed the team to set a research agenda in a non-bias or subjective manner. The interviews were conducted using a video conference call app with

only the participant and interviewer present and lasted an average of one hour. At the start of the interviews, the contents of the research study information document previously shared with the participants were discussed, and verbal consent was obtained to supplement the signed consent forms. The interviews were recorded and later transcribed using anonymised pseudonyms to protect the identity of participants.

3.8 Data Analysis

The transcribed interviews were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2016). The analysis involved immersing oneself in the data to understand the data intimately allowing for identifying emerging patterns and themes across the participants' narratives. This process helped to reveal commonalities and differences in how participants experienced and made sense of living with sickle cell disease. Initially, the research assistant who conducted the interviews read the transcripts and identified preliminary themes. The principal researcher and research assistants then reviewed, analysed, and discussed the transcripts to identify and highlight the main emerging themes. Three main themes and four sub-themes were initially identified. During a further review by the principal researcher, it became clearer that some of the sub-themes were better presented as main themes as there were inherent sub-themes in them, and this interpretation identified five main themes, including subthemes.

3.9 Data Management

Steps were followed to protect the identity of the participants. The collected data and research files were stored in an encrypted and secure folder on a drive. Only the primary researcher and research assistants involved in the study had access to each of their folders. No hard copies of the documents were made or saved. Following the completion of the study, access to the folder will be restricted to the primary researcher and data collected will be terminated following publication of the study. These steps were taken to ensure GDPR protocols are taken to safeguard participants identity.

3.10 Ethics Consideration

Written consent was obtained from each participant prior to participation to account for their voluntary participation. Potentially identifiable data was anonymised, and pseudonyms were used to protect participants' identities. Ethics approval was awarded through the Sickle Cell Society Ireland's Ethics Committee, taking a voluntary sector approach. Participants were informed of the publishing of any data used in the study and consent was given. Distress protocol was put in place to guide research assistants and signpost participants to appropriate support should they require one during or after interviews. Contact numbers for key community leaders and support networks were made available throughout the study duration. This protocol was to safeguard against any potential psychological risk for participants, however, none of these were experienced as the principal investigator, who is a parent of children with sickle cell, and is also a healthcare professional working within therapeutic environments had made initial contact with participants and prepared them for the process.

Limitations and Strengths of the Research Design

The potential for researcher bias was considered and steps were followed to minimise this. Research assistants were trained and debriefed prior to the commencement of the interviews. A semi-structured interview guide and probing questions prepared by the principal researcher were used to ensure a consistent approach was upheld during the interviews while allowing participants to share personal experiences. Meetings were held where collaboration occurred between the principal researcher and research assistants, which engaged multiple perspectives and intimate reflections during the identification of themes in the research. Conducting research with multiple assistants provided several strengths that significantly enhanced the quality and depth of this study. Here are some key strengths:

- 1 Minimisation of Bias:** Utilising multiple research assistants allowed for diverse perspectives and independent analyses, which helped minimise personal biases. This approach ensured that the data collected was more balanced and comprehensive, providing a richer and more accurate depiction of the participants' experiences.
- 2 Enhanced Data Collection:** With a team of assistants, we were able to conduct thorough and in-depth interviews, ensuring a wide range of insights and experiences were captured. This not only increased the volume of data but also its variety, making the findings more robust and reliable.
- 3 Expertise and Professionalism:** The research assistants were well-equipped due to their backgrounds as students of medicine and healthcare and their professional experience within the healthcare field. Their expertise ensured the interviews were conducted with a high level of professionalism and understanding, leading to more meaningful and relevant data.
- 4 Collaborative Learning Environment:** Training and supervising young researchers fostered a culture of learning and collaboration. This not only benefited the assistants, providing them with valuable research experience but also contributed to the study's rigor through continuous dialogue and idea exchange.
- 5 Thorough Data Analysis:** Multiple researchers reviewing and analysing the data increased the depth of the analysis. Each assistant brought their unique perspective, which enriched the thematic analysis and ensured that no significant themes were overlooked.
- 6 Personal Resilience and Advocacy:** My personal journey and the recent loss of my child to sickle cell disease fuelled my determination and resilience. This personal connection drove me to ensure that the research was thorough and impactful, aiming to improve care for patients and their families through evidence-based findings.

By leveraging the strengths of a diverse and skilled team, this research was able to achieve a high standard of thoroughness and depth, ensuring that the findings are both credible and impactful.

3.11 Conclusion

The methodology chapter has detailed the comprehensive and systematic approach taken to explore the lived experiences of individuals with sickle cell disease in Ireland, particularly focusing on their education and employment trajectories. The qualitative design, utilising in-depth one-to-one interviews and thematic analysis, was selected to capture the nuanced and subjective experiences of the participants. Through purposive sampling and a structured recruitment process, a representative sample of individuals fitting the study's criteria was secured. The data collection and analysis processes

were meticulously planned and executed, ensuring rich, detailed insights while maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of the participants' information. Ethical considerations were rigorously adhered to, ensuring the voluntary participation and anonymity of the participants. This chapter underscores the importance of a well-defined methodology in qualitative research, particularly when dealing with sensitive topics such as chronic illness. The steps outlined demonstrate the study's commitment to ethical research practices, thorough data collection, and robust analysis. The insights gained from this study will contribute significantly to the understanding of how sickle cell disease impacts individuals' educational and employment experiences in Ireland, addressing a critical gap in the existing literature. The subsequent chapters will present and discuss the findings derived from this meticulously conducted research, providing a deeper understanding of the participants' lived experiences.

Chapter
4.0
Research Findings
Esther Onolememen

4.1 Introduction

This study explores the daily living experiences of individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland. The five themes that emerged from the interviews highlight the diverse challenges and coping mechanisms of these individuals. We will describe each theme in turn starting with Access to Healthcare.

4.2 Theme One: Access to Healthcare

Access to healthcare for individuals living with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland is fraught with challenges, as revealed through participants' narratives. A recurrent issue highlighted by participants is the inconsistency in accessing care and supportive services and lack of specialised knowledge among general practitioners (GPs), amongst other challenges such as lack of awareness about sickle cell, financial burden and geographical challenges accessing clinics.

A Inconsistencies accessing care:

John expressed frustration with the inconsistency of care due to seeing different doctors each visit. He stated,

"I haven't seen the same person twice... So every single time I have to go in and explain what's going on with them. Or they have to go through my records and then you're starting afresh with a new person." John

Damian shared a similar sentiment, discussing the hurdles in obtaining a medical card. He recalled, an experience of financial strain compounded the difficulty of managing his condition.

"I couldn't get a medical card for some reason because they said my mom was a nurse... So three people, three dependents." Damian

For Damien, the frustration about access seems to be driven by the difficulty of developing a trusting relationship with GP, but also the lack of support from the state to deal with his condition. All this can have contributed to the experience of frustration.

Participants also detailed the stark contrast between paediatric and adult care. Jane noted the difference in the frequency and scheduling of transfusions and check-ups, highlighting the logistical challenges faced by adults.

"...In adults, I'm doing it on two different days. I'll have to come in on Monday for blood tests and then Wednesday for a transfusion... So yeah..." Jane

Israel praised the care provided at Crumlin Children's Hospital, emphasising the priority given to sickle cell patients there.

"...If I'm feeling sick I always just go to Crumlin because they always just give that extra bit of care... There's a priority 100% if you have sickle cell if you go to Crumlin..." Israel

Tia contrasted her experiences in Ireland with those in Nigeria, noting a significant improvement in the quality and attentiveness of healthcare. She appreciated the comprehensive diagnostics and follow-up care, stating,

"...They listen more to the patients. They care about you and they follow up... They checked all my organs. They checked whether I was sickling in every part of my body..." Tia

B Financial Burden

Participants consistently reported significant financial challenges due to the costs associated with managing sickle cell disease. Damian highlighted the heavy financial toll of hospital stays, stating,

"...Like the first one in Crumlin... I think it was like 200 euros or something. And the second time... I stayed there for longer and... that ended up in like 600 plus euros. So I had to pay that out of pocket..." (Damian)

The cost of essential medications was also a major concern. Damian shared his experience with nutritional supplements prescribed by a dietician:

“...They are quite expensive... after my dad buying them for like maybe five times it just kind of burned my dad’s wallet...” Damian

The lack of automatic eligibility for a medical card for those with sickle cell disease exacerbates these financial strains. Damian shared his experience of significant out-of-pocket expenses for hospital stays, which he believed could be alleviated with better medical card provisions. This sentiment reflects a broader call for systemic support to alleviate the financial burdens faced by individuals with chronic illnesses. He stated:

“I think if you have sickle cell you should automatically be given a medical card... because it’s something where you’re going to have constant hospital visits...” Damian

C Geographical Barriers

Geographical barriers also played a significant role in participants’ accessibility and quality of care. For those living in rural or less serviced areas, reaching specialised healthcare facilities was found to be very challenging as some of the participants stated. For them, it means their access to treatment and care is sometimes delayed and can lead to increased health risks according to participants, and it compounds the struggle with accessing timely and adequate care.

The combined financial and geographical challenges force individuals and their families to make difficult choices about their care and wellbeing. For participants, this includes rationing medication, delaying or forgoing treatments, and enduring suboptimal living conditions during hospital stays. Damian described a particularly harsh experience during a hospital visit in winter, which underscored the need for improved healthcare infrastructure and support systems tailored to the needs of people with sickle cell disease.

“They didn’t have the radiator in the room they put me in. So here I was freezing in January... and I kept asking for more blankets...” Damian

The narratives of participants in this study illuminate the urgent need for policy interventions to address both the financial and geographical barriers to healthcare. Ensuring equitable access to medical cards and enhancing the reach of healthcare services can significantly improve the quality of life for those living with sickle cell disease in Ireland.

D Lack of Awareness and Information

Both Israel and Paul pointed out the lack of awareness about sickle cell disease in Ireland. Israel noted that many people are unaware of the benefits and allowances they are eligible for, such as disability allowances.

“...I know a lot of people who don’t know what disability allowance is... there’s just not enough information out there...” Israel

Paul emphasised the public’s ignorance about the disease, which sometimes leads to misunderstandings and lack of proper support at workplaces and schools.

“...People don’t get it. They don’t understand sickle cell. It makes school and work really hard sometimes...” Paul

Overall, the findings indicate a need for more consistent and specialised care for adults with SCD in Ireland, improved access to medical cards, and better awareness among healthcare professionals regarding the complexities of managing SCD.

E Lack of Awareness among Healthcare Professionals

Participants highlighted a significant lack of awareness about sickle cell disease among healthcare professionals in Ireland. For participants, this lack of knowledge often resulted in them having to educate their own healthcare providers about their condition. One participant, Paul, shared his frustration:

"...Yeah see? Like that's why I was saying like you could go to like any random therapist, you know, but the chances of them even knowing what sickle cell even is, is low. Cause they might know, they might not know. I don't know but I just feel like based on what I know they don't [know about sickle cell]. I don't think many therapists even know what sickle cell is. You probably have to explain to them as well..." Paul

F Lack of Public Awareness

Participants' expressed that in their experience, they have observed that the general public's understanding of sickle cell disease is lacking. For them, this can lead to misconceptions and lack of support in their everyday situations. Paul emphasised the necessity for broader awareness:

"...I would say a lot of people don't - A lot of people don't have any idea what it is in Ireland. I would say so, but it's just something where there needs to be... the majority of the public should know what it is and how to, you know, get along with people that have it or whatever. Cause like the problems I was having at work. If it was a thing where my boss knew or had any idea of what I had, I believe he wouldn't be acting that way..." Paul

4.3 Theme Two: Stigma and Psychological/Mental Health Impact

Stigma and psychological impact of sickle cell disease on individuals living with sickle cell disease in Ireland was found consistent in the interviews with respondents, and substantially, affecting their mental health, social interactions, and overall quality of life. The importance of psychological support and understanding from both the medical community and social circles was deemed crucial in alleviating some of these burdens according to participants. Findings touched on the impact of living with the disease and managing care on a daily basis, and coming to terms with the extent to which the lack of awareness and proper support affects individuals mentally.

A Stigma

Many participants highlighted the stigma associated with sickle cell disease, which often leads to feelings of isolation and misunderstanding. For instance, Israel explained how he had to educate his friends and peers about his condition because they were generally uninformed. He stated,

"...I told my friends and my parents told my school. I'd tell my friends I'd always tell my friends you know that I had it. My friends didn't know much about it. So I would always inform them..." Israel

Paul echoed similar sentiments, noting that his friends were unaware of what sickle cell was until he explained it to them. He mentioned,

"I had to explain everything to them. Yeah. But that's just because that's just because the - the people like that close to me that's just like in case anything happens..." Paul

B Psychological/Mental Health Impact

The psychological impact of living with sickle cell disease is profound, with many participants reporting feelings of anxiety, depression, and a general sense of being overwhelmed, coupled with the lack of awareness and understanding of sickle cell disease, which also contributed to the experiences of mental health challenges among patients.

Paul described the psychological burden:

“...Sometimes it also affects my mental state cause I always have dark thoughts. Sometimes when I have the time when I'm just alone and I go into the dark state of thinking. I could sometimes just be thinking that anything could happen anytime to me without me knowing like anything could just happen...” Paul

Jane highlighted the mental strain of managing her condition, she expressed:

“...In terms of like taking medication coming in like it's just like very like mentally draining. And so it's nice to like be able to speak to someone that you don't know and just kind of like unpack...” Jane

Jane also noted the significant positive impact of receiving psychological support:

“...They introduced the psychologist to me and that was she was really really helpful ... because I was very dismissive of it 'I was like oh this is not going to help me I don't really see the point' and so when she was introduced to me I was like wow this is actually really helpful...” Jane

Damian discussed the constant mental battle and the pessimism that can arise from living with the disease. He shared,

“...It kind of got to a point where I was almost pessimistic but I tried to be optimistic. I tried to be happy and this and that but every now and then if you're in the kitchen or something making food you're just in your thoughts and then you're just like oh wait I have this disease and that spirals into something else...” Damian

John Doe talked about the impact on his outlook on life and relationships, mentioning,

“...I always try not to like look too far ahead If you get me like getting my hopes up like I'm gonna go get married soon. I'm gonna do this I'm gonna have kids. I'm just like you're vibing yeah so I guess it affected some sort of friendship because like I don't be going out of my way to like get friendships cause I'm just like what's the point?...” John Doe

4.4 Theme Three: Social and Family Support Systems – Impact on Family and Friends

This theme captured the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with sickle cell disease in Ireland, affecting their education, employment, and family dynamics, with significant reliance on support systems to manage their daily lives. The narratives of participants were consistent in highlighting the profound impact of family and friends on the daily living experiences of individuals with sickle cell disease in Ireland, identifying the essential role of support networks in managing the challenges of the condition. Their narratives reveal a spectrum of experiences, from supportive work environments to those requiring significant personal advocacy and adjustment. The impact of SCD on employment was found multifaceted, affecting job choices, performance, and overall job satisfaction.

A Support Network: Family Involvement

The role of family members as primary caregivers and emotional support is critical for individuals living with sickle cell disease. Participants highlighted the indispensable support their families provide, emphasising the impact on their well-being and daily functioning.

Jane Loe (JL) expressed that while her friends are aware of her condition, she doesn't discuss it extensively with them.

“...Yeah yeah yeah they know about it. It’s not something that I would like really like. speak on it loads. I just be like okay I have my appointment today or this is like like say if I travel or something like I take my medication in front of them, but it wouldn’t be something like I’m like talking about loads to them...” Jane Loe

John Doe (JD) shared that his mother, being a nurse, played a crucial role in managing his health at home.

“...My mom is in the medical line so she’s a nurse and she was my primary health caregiver. So, I didn’t have a lot of trips to the hospital. Most of the crises were being managed by her at home”. He also emphasized her continuous support, “My mum is really, really supportive because then she’s like how are you doing? Hope you’re doing, okay? Have you taken this? Have you taken that? Make sure you keep warm. Don’t do too much...” John Doe

Damian highlighted the comprehensive support from his family, stating,

“...My family understands it the most. And obviously I feel safest in their care. My friends can probably do or try their best but it’s not the same...” Damian

He also expressed concerns about independence, and shared the emotional burden he felt he puts on his family,

“...I just kind of thought if I start living alone and I get sick then what? Who’s going to call the ambulance? Who’s going to drive me to the hospital... like any time I get sick they just drop everything they’re doing... I hate the fact that people have to sacrifice their life for, you know, just me...” Damian

B Friends’ Awareness and Support

Participants also discussed the varying degrees of awareness and support from friends. Israel described how his friends and school were informed about his condition. In addition, he discussed how his older sister’s career choice in physiotherapy was influenced by her experience supporting him through intensive physiotherapy sessions during a severe crisis.

“...I told my friends and my parents told my school. I would tell my friends I would always tell my friends you know that I had it. My friends did not know much about it. So I would always inform them...” Israel

Paul mentioned that he often had to explain his condition to his friends.

“...I had to explain everything to them... But that’s just because the people close to me, that’s just in case anything happens...” Paul

C Emotional Support and Coping Strategies

Having a network of peers with similar experiences was identified as a significant coping mechanism for most of the participants. Tia found comfort in connecting with other individuals living with sickle cell disease. She noted the positive impact of meeting others with the condition in Ireland, which helped her cope better

“...I feel more comfortable and more relaxed when I share my problem with another sickle cell patient...” Tia

Damian also expressed how he benefited from the support of a specific friend during crises.

“...I have one specific friend... whenever I’m in crisis and things like that I will talk to her and she’s amazing because like she’s always making sure she checks up on me, texting me, just keeping me busy and trying to keep my mind active...” Damian

4.5 Theme Four: Impact on Education

All participants were consistent in their responses about how their experience of living with sickle cell impacts their education. For example, Jane Loe noted that her condition did not significantly affect her attendance during primary and secondary school. However, as an adult, the complexity of managing her healthcare appointments increased. Jane emphasised the challenges of balancing her educational commitments with her health needs and how she faced logistical challenges due to her condition. She shared:

“...In children’s hospitals, they’ll try and schedule like blood tests and X-rays on the same day you come in for transfusion. With the adult hospital, it’s a lot harder...I’m going to have to try and condense my days...I can’t do anything afterwards, I have to be at home resting...when I go back to school in September, I’m going to have to condense my days because I’ll be on placement and need to be there Monday to Friday. After my transfusion, I can’t do anything else; I have to rest...” Jane Loe

Participants also discussed the impact of lack of awareness on their educational experiences. Tia, a participant, reflected on how her condition and the lack of understanding from teachers and peers affected her:

“...Since when I was in secondary school I never participated in any extracurricular activities. And that really affected me a lot and it reduced my self-esteem...” Tia

Tia also discussed the impact of frequent sick leaves on her education, particularly during her time in college. Despite these challenges, she acknowledged the support from her university:

“...For this semester I wasn’t in class...I missed a lot of information.” “But when I was sick...I was able to fill out some form saying I was sick. I don’t think it will affect my grade...” Tia

Israel shared that he did not disclose his condition to his university. He expressed he only informed his student coach about potential accommodations but has not yet needed to use this support.

“...My university friends don’t even know I have sickle cell. I just never told them...” Israel

Paul recounted how his condition, coupled with bullying in school, significantly impacted his educational experience. He mentioned how he started being less interested in going to school day by day, and eventually lost interest in finishing school. This disinterest extended into his transition year during the COVID-19 pandemic, affecting his overall academic performance.

John shared how he experienced a severe crisis during his final exams, which forced him to write an exam while lying down due to extreme pain. This incident highlights the physical toll of the disease during critical academic periods. Additionally, he shared how he felt his aspirations were limited by his condition:

“...I remember my last paper...I was so sick that I actually laid down to write the exam.” “I always had to keep bringing down my dreams...because I just wouldn’t be able to perform on par...” Paul

4.6 Theme Five: Accessing Employment and its Challenges

The challenges faced by individuals living with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland significantly impact their employment opportunities and experiences. Participants shared their struggles with disclosing their condition, managing their health alongside work commitments, and the perceptions and accommodations (or lack thereof) from employers.

John discussed the difficulties of pacing himself in his job as a photographer. He stated:

"...I try to always pace myself. If it's becoming too stressful, I either ask for extra help or slow down a bit and not rush it. I have to be cautious at work because I don't want to fall sick. That's where I see it the most..." John

Damian provided insight into his experience working in the public sector. He also noted his career choice was influenced by his condition, choosing IT because it involved less physical activity and could be done remotely. He explained,

"...I've only worked in the public sector. The government has laws to protect me, so even if I end up falling sick, I won't lose my job. The worst that will happen is not getting paid for those times..." Damian

Israel stated that his sickle cell had not hindered his ability to work in various roles. He remarked,

"...I don't feel like my sickle cell has hindered me in working. I've worked sales assistant jobs, retail, and as a waiter. Some of my employers knew, but I didn't feel the need to tell all of them. It didn't really affect me..." Israel

Paul highlighted financial pressures influencing his work decisions. He said,

"...I have to keep working full-time to support myself through college and pay rent. I've had issues getting time off in my old workplace, where my head chef didn't believe I needed the time for appointments. But my current workplace is more accommodating..." Paul

4.7 Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with SCD in Ireland. These challenges include inconsistent healthcare, significant financial burdens, impacts on employment and education, and profound psychological and social implications. The transition from paediatric to adult care was particularly found problematic, with participants expressing concerns about the quality and consistency of adult healthcare services. The financial strains associated with managing SCD necessitate systemic support, such as automatic eligibility for medical cards to alleviate out-of-pocket expenses. Additionally, the psychological and social challenges underscore the need for comprehensive support systems to address the holistic needs of individuals with SCD.

Chapter
5.0
Discussion

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5.1 Introduction

This chapter synthesises the findings of the research on the lived experiences of individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in Ireland, drawing on qualitative data from participant interviews and existing literature. The discussion aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted challenges faced by those with SCD, including healthcare access, psychosocial impacts, educational attainment, employment, and social support networks. By examining these themes, this chapter seeks to contextualise the research findings within the broader landscape of SCD management and care, identifying critical gaps and proposing areas for improvement. Through this analysis, the chapter underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions to enhance the quality of life for individuals living with SCD in Ireland.

5.2 Access to Healthcare for People Living with Sickle Cell

In the Literature it was found that many people with SCD experience severe complications (Bailey et al., 2020; Rizio et al.2020). These can be due to VOC leading to clots that can lodge anywhere in the body and cut off the blood supply. This can also be due to the increased risk of infection as well as the need for frequent hospital visits and the use of implanted medical devices. This was the case with one participant, Paul, who spent a significant amount of time in the hospital with an infection and Covid.

One participant experienced a pain crisis severe enough that it brought him to the Hospital. But found the cost of care in the ED prohibitive. Brousseau et al. (2010), a US study, found that most people with SCD present to the Emergency department due to the severity of the pain and potential complications associated with VOC.

According to the HSE's clinical strategy and programmes division for non-malignant haematological diseases (accessed April 19th 2024), SCD is primarily cared for in Dublin and Cork for both

paediatric and adult patients and in Galway, for adults primarily. The majority of participants specifically mentioned their preference for visiting the SCD specialised children's Hospital. This was preferred over the adult SCD specialised hospital ED, other Hospital's EDs, and over their general practitioners. This was due to long wait times accrued in these other locations and lack of knowledge and understanding from GPs and ED healthcare workers. This is consistent with Al Jubri et al., a study conducted in London which found similar results in that people with SCD tend to utilise and receive better care from Hospital EDs rather than GPs. Benjamin et al. outlines how important it is to cut down on wait times to prevent complications, and reduce pain and suffering. Swallmeh et al. 2018 found in Ireland that participants experienced long waits, poor communication from healthcare staff and poor communications about delays in EDs. Most participants praised the treatment they received from practitioners at the children's SCD Hospital and spoke about lack of knowledge by their GPs and healthcare staff in other hospitals, and long wait times in other Dublin Hospitals. Unfortunately as this is a paediatric hospital, and most of the participants are in their late teens to early twenties, they are faced with the challenge that they know the treatment from one hospital is superior and the practitioners there are more knowledgeable, but as they are now adults they may be required to go to different hospitals, especially in the case of an illness requiring hospital admission. It is important to note that in a study conducted in the Netherlands specialised healthcare workers who are knowledgeable about the treatment of SCD report that many GPs have limited knowledge on the treatment and care for people with SCD (Houwing et al. 2021). Al Jubri et al. a study conducted in London, found a similar lack of SCD knowledge by GPs.

The literature outlines how many with SCD choose to go to a hospital over a GP because of the GPs lack of knowledge (Keane and Defoe, 2016). This sentiment was found in our participants as well. Most do not feel that their GPs have a good understanding of their condition or how to treat it. Two participants spoke on how they had to inform their GPs of all their medications and that the GP did no review and had little to no prior knowledge. One participant mentioned that he is still ordering all of his medications from his home country of Nigeria due to the combined barriers

of lack of GP knowledge, cost of care in Ireland, and lack of government funded care. Another participant recalled a particular pain crisis where he tried to attend the ED but the cost was prohibitive so he had his GP give him prescription painkillers. He had to administer his own care using only these and what he had in his home, often being unable to leave his bed. This pain crisis lasted multiple days with only this treatment available and could have led to much more serious complications.

Geographical Challenges and travel time

As previously mentioned the treatment centres for SCD in Ireland are in Dublin and Cork for paediatrics and adults, and Galway for adults only. This limits where people can live in Ireland but also in the cities of Dublin and Cork as some of these patients need to travel to Hospital for 1 or 2 days of treatment every 3-5 weeks, and others have frequent doctor visits and need, or feel more comfortable, in close proximity to an emergency room, where they know there are knowledgeable physicians and staff. There is also a very high cost of living in the city of Dublin, as well as limited housing availability. Most participants mentioned difficulty finding suitable housing at some or multiple points in their life. All of this travel and treatment takes up a large proportion of these people's lives, even more so if they have long distances to travel. It also makes living anywhere away from these cities nearly impossible. This aligns with Buchanan et al. 2006 and Smeltzer et al. 2016 who identified the challenges of receiving care when living in a rural community, especially compared to more urban counterparts. Houwing et al. Speaks on travel expenses and distance to hospital as a significant barrier to treatment. These difficulties align with our findings.

Some people with SCD are treated with transfusions. This treatment requires new blood testing every time, they are then required to be available most of the following day for the actual transfusion. This is already a significant time commitment and when people have a large distance to travel, or are reliant on public transportation, this can be a significant barrier to receiving adequate healthcare. One interviewee receives blood transfusions every five weeks, while

another receives transfusions every three weeks. He is also reliant on public transportation and since he requires 1 full day off for the transfusion every three weeks he often has to use his lunch breaks to complete the required blood testing as he is unable to secure both days off of work.

Medical and Financial challenges

The Irish healthcare system has a lot of support for the young, the elderly, and many with chronic disease, but unfortunately SCD is not included in the conditions that qualify someone for the long term illness scheme. The purpose of the long term illness scheme is to provide financial support to people whose conditions will affect them and have a significant financial burden for their entire life. Despite the chronicity of SCD, including blood tests and transfusions for some, it is not included in the list of lifelong conditions.

<https://www2.hse.ie/services/schemes-allowances/lti/approved-medications/>

Despite the chronicity, financial burden, and potential for SCD to cause a long or short-term inability to work, only one of the interviewees has a medical card, and none have disability allowance. It is of note that one participant had a medical card as a child but was not approved for renewal as an adult despite recommendations from his physicians and care team at the paediatric hospital.

The literature has identified many financial challenges including costs of medication, hospital visits, medications and other treatments as well as the need to maintain warm temperatures indoors (Keane and Defoe, 2016). All of these challenges and more were brought up by the participants. For some the cost of care in hospital is so prohibitive that they avoid it altogether. One participant goes to his mother for care because he cannot afford the ED costs. Two of the other participants also mention that they avoid hospital visits if at all possible. Three out of six participants mention contributing hugely to their own treatment plan, stating that it is necessary for them to inform their GPs on their condition and required medications as the GPs are so uninformed on SCD and SCD care. While medication and avoiding hospital visits

is the bare minimum required to keep people with SCD healthy enough to function, medication alone is the bare minimum, the medications are not cheap, and there is no disability allowance awarded to people with SCD in Ireland.

5.3 Psychosocial Impact: Stigma, Psychological/Mental Health Impact

In several studies done in West Africa and the USA surrounding the psychosocial ramifications of Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), a recurrent theme established is the poor psychosocial well-being of persons living with SCD. These studies emphasise the substantial interconnection between SCD and the development of psychological disorders such as depression and anxiety (Harris et al. 2023) (Onyeaka et al. 2019) Although, in Ireland, research on this topic is very limited, our findings align with these observations. In our study, participants discussed experiences with poor mental health, depression and anxiety associated with their diagnosis and or symptoms. Five out of six participants expressed SCD causing significant mental burden due to its psychosomatic effects, as seen in literature (Tylee et al. 2005) (Chaturvedi, 2013.) These findings from the participant interviews illustrate the critical role of adequate support systems in managing these difficulties. One participant discussed the initial lack of access to knowledgeable mental health care professionals regarding the impact of SCD, leading to a negative psychological impact. She described being allocated a social worker, who unfortunately did not have the tools and or enough knowledge of SCD to adequately assist her in regards to the mental load of SCD thus making the sessions futile. However, this was subsequently remedied by the appointment of a psychologist who befittingly aided the participant in coping with the strain of SCD, in contrast to the limited efficacy of the previous sessions. This further strengthens the need for a more specialised support system within the Irish healthcare system to address and manage the unique mental health challenges faced by individuals with SCD. Another participant emphasised the pervasive fear of premature demise due to SCD which led to the avoidance of future

planning; a common sentiment shared amongst other participants. Similarly, a participant discussed the constant feeling of anxiety, pessimism and feeling like a burden to others, leading to a hesitation in making significant life changes which further highlights the element of the unpredictability of SCD. In addition, one participant subsequently highlighted the experience of somatization which exacerbates her SCD due to stress; such is concurrent with the aforementioned literature which further demonstrates the complex relationship between psychological stress and overall health in individuals with SCD.

In contrast, one participant maintained a positive outlook on their mental health due to receiving extensive support from family and friends in view of their vast knowledge and experience with SCD. This personal support contributed greatly to the individuals overall well-being and emotional stability. However, this participant did not speak about support from medical professionals, further highlighting the gap in the Irish healthcare system's ability to provide patients with comprehensive care for their SCD. Our findings intensify the essential role that personal support networks play in addressing the psychosocial challenges of SCD whilst also underlining the urgent need for medical professionals in Ireland to be equally well-informed and proactive in providing thorough mental health care to individuals living with SCD.

In our study, the narrative of stigmatisation and ignorance of SCD showed the profound link between societal perceptions of SCD and the negative influences on the mental health of those living with the disease. Upon reviewing various literature, studies have consistently shown negative societal attitudes toward SCD lead to increased detrimental health and social outcomes. A study done in Nigeria stated 60% of adults and adolescents had reported they felt the general public held a negative societal attitude about SCD and less than one-third reported experiencing teasing or bullying throughout their education and employment (Anie et al. 2010). Though there are no such statistics in Ireland, it was found that stigma and lack of awareness of SCD can hinder open dialogue and support for persons with SCD. This was exemplified in our study with one participant describing his experience of having to explain his condition to his entire social circle in fear of the event

of a SCD crisis which contributed to the emotional burden of managing the disease whilst simultaneously bearing responsibility of educating his social circles.

Hospitalisations are known to be anxiety-inducing for people living with SCD. In a study exploring distressing experiences identified by people living with SCD, they were found to describe their encounters in acute care settings as anger, frustration, and bewilderment-inducing (Childerhose et al. (2024). A notable theme identified amongst participants of this study is the disparity between treatment in paediatric hospitals as compared to that of adult hospitals. Four out of six participants specifically highlighted the difference in how their appointments and treatments were managed as they made the transition from paediatric to adult care. They described medical professionals in the treatment of their SCD as adults, as appearing less emotionally connected and less attuned to their specific needs. Appointments in adult care were perceived as more robotic and impersonal in contrast to their experiences in paediatric care where medical professionals endeavoured to know them beyond their SCD diagnosis such as in their education which helped to foster good rapport and a trusting relationship. This shift in dynamics of care further increases the need for more empathetic and tailored care for all individuals living with SCD in order to reduce distress during hospitalisations and improve patient outcomes. Studies also state that some healthcare providers do not believe or are not willing to accept the level of pain that individuals with SCD suffer with as they attribute it to an addiction with no substantial evidence that would suggest this other than their own perceptions (Ezenwa et al. 2016) This correlates with our, study with one participant describing attending the hospital during a crisis and having to wait in the Emergency Department for an extended period of time whilst in excruciating pain as no medical professional intervened until many hours later, further exacerbating his already difficult condition. He was then subsequently given a hospital room with poor heating during the winter, until a nurse created a makeshift heating pad for him. Existing literature states that temperature changes, especially cold weather, can trigger SCD crises by increasing pain sensitivity (Brandow et al. 2019). Therefore his experience highlights the critical need for appropriate and timely medical intervention for individuals living

with SCD as well as maintaining an environment that mitigates pain triggers such as adequate heating in hospital rooms to prevent additional complications and help to alleviate anxiety and frustration associated with hospitalisation.

5.4 The Impact of Accessing Education for People Living with Sickle Cell

The impact of SCD on education is quite multifaceted; It is seen to greatly affect one's attendance, academic performance and socialisation. Studies have proven SCD to be linked to a deficient academic performance and poor educational attainment patterns Fowler (1988). We found our study to be in line with these studies with all six participants mentioning SCD having an impact on their education in various ways, revealing a range of experiences and challenges.

In our study, one participant highlighted the contrasting difference between her experience of SCD in regard to its impact in her primary and secondary education as compared to tertiary education. She stated her attendance in the lower levels of education not being significantly affected, however this was not the circumstance as she started university. As she transitioned into adult healthcare for her SCD, many complications presented themselves due to less coordinated medical appointment scheduling which led to ramifications in her ability to attend classes consistently. In view of this, a recurrent theme which has been discussed by participants of this study is the distinction between paediatric and adult care, which was again corroborated by this participant. The participant stated she had found adult care less adaptable than paediatric care where efforts were made to minimise educational disruption. In Paediatric care, all medical appointments were often scheduled together with educational support provided during hospital stays in order to prevent her falling behind her peers. In contrast, adult care often lacked this consideration leading to a higher level of absenteeism from university thus creating challenges in maintaining a consistent level of education. Due

to the lack of educational support in adult care, this participant found it difficult to keep up with the demands of university resulting in an increased level of stress in balancing both her health and academics. This gap between educational support in paediatric care in comparison to that of adult care underlines another area in need for improvement in adult SCD care in Ireland in order to ensure that individuals especially adults with SCD that are in education can continue their education with adequate support and minimal disruption.

In another study conducted in the UK Dyson et al (2010) found that over three quarters of the young people in said study reported negative school experiences such as being prevented from using the toilet, prevented from drinking water, made do unsuitable exercise or called lazy when tired. These findings align with our study, where one participant recounted his experience of bullying due to his physical appearance, a result of the visible symptoms of SCD. This negative social experience led to his significantly decreased interest in education, leading to disengagement, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic where social interaction was already very limited. The toll of bullying can be anxiety-inducing and cause low self-esteem and as a result, these mental challenges can further exacerbate the difficulties faced by students with SCD. Despite these setbacks, this participant expressed a renewed interest in pursuing further education, encouraged by a newfound passion. This illustrates how individuals with SCD may find alternative pathways to fulfilment despite the hindrance to education posed by their health condition.

Another participant had described having a generally supportive environment during his primary education years, where he found teachers to be well-informed about his condition and responsive to his specific needs, this support made a notable difference in his ability to manage his health and education concurrently. However, as he progressed into secondary education and university, there was a shift in the level of awareness and support subsequently decreased creating a new challenge in navigating his education journey. This led to a personal decision to not disclose his condition to his university authorities and rely instead on informal support from a student

coach. His experience shows the variability in support systems in education for those with SCD and the personal choices individuals with the condition may make about disclosing their health condition, this decision often influenced by past experiences and a perceived level of understanding of SCD in their current environment.

In a study conducted in the United States Crosby et al. (2015) it was discovered that 40% of the participants had repeated a grade during their time in school while 37% had received special education services. The available data indicates a link between the severity of illness, medical complications and school absences which collectively affect performance and educational achievements. Our research study agrees with this finding as one participant shared his struggles with disruptions to his education due to sickle cell crises especially during crucial academic periods. The participants' hospitalisations resulted in missed deadlines hindering academic progress and negatively impacting his mental well-being. These interruptions led to a loss of motivation leading him to opt for a lower degree qualification level than initially intended. Similarly another participant stated the stress associated with exams often triggered a sickle cell crisis which led to a reduced academic performance. In addition to the hindrance of SCD in academics, the physical limitations of the illness influenced this participant's career aspirations with him initially wanting to be an astronaut or pilot but due to the physical demands of these professions he had to lower his expectations, leading him to choose a less physically demanding career that is deemed more compatible with SCD. These participants' experiences emphasises the emotional and psychological toll of managing SCD alongside academic obligations. The constant need to balance medical need with responsibilities creates a burdensome environment that can severely hinder a student's drive and ability to excel academically, emphasising the importance of establishing better support systems within educational institutions for students with chronic illnesses like SCD in Ireland.

As seen in our study, SCD is seen to significantly impact education in many different ways. Factors such as the level of support in healthcare, flexibility of educational institutions, social dynamics and personal

resilience play immense roles in controlling how substantially SCD affects one's education. The diverse and complex anecdotes of the participants show the need for more support systems within the Irish Education system and emphasise the need for policies that accommodate the adversities experienced by those with SCD.

5.5 Impact on Accessing Employment for people Living with Sickle Cell

All of the participants were found to have made alterations to their jobs or chose to work in specific lower-impact fields due to the difficulties and sometimes unpredictable nature of SCD. While Dyson and Berghs (2020) suggest disclosure of SCD status may be beneficial towards creating reasonable accommodations, Franklin and Atkin, 1986 spoke on the possibility of employers deciding, consciously or through unconscious bias, not to hire people with SCD due to anticipation of unreliability. Franklin et al. 1986 also noted that in general, employers in the UK west midlands had no general understanding of SCD. This lack of accommodations at work and lack of general knowledge of SCD by employers was consistent with the participants' experience. One participant elected to condense blood tests and transfusions, procedures usually done on different days, into one long day because she was only able to guarantee one day off of work. Another participant has a similar issue and often needs to get his blood testing done on his lunch break. Berghs (2021) spoke on the concept of SCD as an invisible disability leading to colleagues and employers considering people with SCD as undeserving of work accommodations as they were not perceived as sick. This is consistent with all participants' experience. One, in particular, had an employer that refused to believe in SCD and was convinced the participant simply wanted more days off. This speaks to the lack of general knowledge of SCD held by the majority of the Irish population.

Two participants' chose to work for themselves in jobs that can be done from home. This negates the need to explain their condition to employers and risk

the misunderstanding. This is consistent with the literature, Dyson and Berghs (2020) found a significant number of people with SCD chose self-employment in the UK. Thomas and Taylor, 2003 found that people with SCD have a greater degree of difficulty securing and maintaining jobs. This is consistent with our findings, in that all participants had to take great care in which jobs and job fields they are able to work in, as well as the decision of whether or not to talk about their SCD. One participant spoke of purposely working in the public sector so his job would be government-protected even if he needed significant time off for health purposes.

It is important to note that none of our participants' places of employment had preset SCD accommodations in place prior to their employment. This is consistent with the literature findings on lack of general knowledge as well as the tendency for employers to ignore the increased need for self-care by SCD individuals (Franklin et al. 1986) (Dyson et al. 2021).

5.6 Impact on Family and Friends (support network)

Alongside both the physical and psychosocial effects of SCD, SCD also permeates the interpersonal relationships of those living with the disease, exerting a profound impact on the individuals' families and social networks. Families of those of individuals with SCD describe the impact of the disease as burdensome, stressful and demanding (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000). This corresponds with our study with one participant conferring receiving substantial support from both their family and friends though mentioned a reluctance to frequently discussing her condition with friends for fear of burdening them. This testifies the nuance between individuals with SCD seeking support from others whilst maintaining an element of privacy due to the guilt of being a potential burden to others.

Literature states, a majority of caregiver burden disproportionately falls on mothers (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000; Karadag et al, 2018) This is in

agreement within our study with one participant reflecting on the essential role of support from his mother particularly in helping to manage his SCD, with her providing primary health care as a medical professional during crisis' reducing the need for hospital intervention. Her constant vigilance and proactive care were quite pivotal in managing her child's condition at home. This further highlights the profound impact of maternal support in mitigating the physical and emotional toll of SCD, demonstrating the indispensable role mothers often assume in these families with individuals with SCD.

In research published by (Karadağ et al,) all research participants expressed fears of losing their child due to SCD. This literature is echoed in one participant's interview where during a long hospital stay as a result of a severe SCD crisis, his father expressed doubts in his ability to ever live alone safely without the care of his parents. This participants' experience illustrates the intense dependency on family reinforced by the constant fear of severe SCD crisis' and or death as seen in the prior mentioned literature. Another study denoted that parents of children with the condition reported an intense focus on their child, particularly during health crises, leading them to feel as if their personal lives were on hold Atkin and Ahmad (2000) This again coincided with our study as one participant described the substantial support provided to him by his family whereby they would "drop everything" in order to care for him during his SCD crisis'. Although he vocalised his gratitude to his family, he felt an immense sense of guilt as a result of the sacrifices they have had to make in their personal lives for the sake of his poor health. The theme of sacrifice was also subsequently discussed by another participant. During his interview, he recounted the support he received from a sibling who chose a career in physiotherapy by reason of his condition, as a result of being given the news in his adolescence that he may never walk again due to complications of his SCD. This further illustrates the profound impact SCD can have on family dynamics and their career and life choices.

Participants also discussed the roles of friends in providing emotional support. One participant spoke of having one friend whom he can confide in and who helps distract him from the pain of SCD when he is having a crisis. This same participant also spoke of

a worldwide online chat room that was created by individuals with SCD to share their perspectives on living with the disease. Another participant also shared the same sentiment, though she stated finding it easier to confide in other individuals that also have SCD due to the common background and them possessing a better level of understanding of her daily experience with the disease. This further underlines the need for a strong social support network beyond the immediate family and the desire for a community of people with similar experiences.

Despite these challenges, families commonly considered their children as courageous, calling them "sickle cell warriors" proudly acknowledging their bravery and resilience in spite of the disease's challenges (Atkin and Ahmad, 2000) Framing their experience as positive is very crucial for maintaining the general morale of the family and the child's self-esteem. This supportive environment not only uplifts the child's psyche but also creates a sense of determination and unity within the family, making it easier to navigate the daily struggles associated with SCD.

5.7 Conclusion

The discussion chapter has provided a nuanced understanding of the complex and multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in Ireland. The synthesis of qualitative data and existing literature has highlighted critical areas where significant gaps and systemic barriers persist, impacting the lives of those with SCD. The research underscores the pressing need for improved access to specialised healthcare services. The geographic concentration of treatment centres in major cities like Dublin and Cork, coupled with long wait times and high costs, significantly hampers the ability of SCD patients to receive timely and adequate care. The transition from pediatric to adult care presents additional hurdles, often resulting in decreased quality of care and increased logistical challenges.

The analysis revealed that the psychosocial burdens of SCD, including depression, anxiety, and societal stigma, profoundly affect the mental health and overall

well-being of individuals. Compounded by the lack of specialised mental health support and the pervasive stigma surrounding SCD exacerbates these challenges for respondents, leading to feelings of isolation and inadequate emotional support.

The discussion identified correlations with existing literature on how educational attainment for individuals with SCD is significantly disrupted by frequent medical appointments and hospitalisations. The study reveals how the transition from pediatric to adult care often results in reduced educational support, further hindering academic progress. There is a critical need for consistent and tailored support within educational institutions to ensure that students with SCD can achieve their full academic potential.

Employment presented substantial challenges, with most respondents opting for lower-impact jobs or self-employment to manage their condition. We noted that the lack of awareness and accommodations in the workplace leads to job insecurity and additional stress, highlighting the need for increased employer awareness and proactive measures to support employees with SCD.

We found that Family and friends play a crucial role in providing emotional and practical support, yet this often comes at a significant cost to caregivers, particularly mothers. The reliance on personal support networks underscores the need for comprehensive and specialised support services to alleviate the burden on families and provide holistic care for SCD patients.

In conclusion, addressing the needs of individuals with SCD in Ireland requires a coordinated, multifaceted approach involving healthcare providers, policymakers, support organisations, and the broader community. The findings from this discussion highlight the critical areas for intervention, providing a foundation for targeted recommendations aimed at improving the quality of life for individuals with SCD. By enhancing healthcare access, integrating mental health support, providing consistent educational and employment accommodations, and strengthening social support networks, substantial progress can be made towards ensuring comprehensive and compassionate care for individuals living with SCD in Ireland.

Chapter
6.0
Recommendations
Esther Onolememen

6.1 Introduction

The recommendations presented in this chapter aim to address the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland. Drawing from the research findings and discussions, these recommendations are intended to enhance healthcare services, increase public awareness, and provide comprehensive support systems for affected individuals.

6.2 Recommendations for Healthcare Providers

1 Enhance training for healthcare professionals:

- A key finding of this research is the lack of adequate knowledge and training among healthcare professionals regarding SCD. Developing comprehensive training programmes will equip medical staff with the necessary skills and understanding to manage SCD effectively. Training should include both the medical aspects of SCD and cultural competence to address the diverse backgrounds of patients. By improving healthcare professionals' knowledge, patients can receive better, more empathetic care.
- **Action:** Implement regular training sessions, workshops, and continuing education programmes focusing on the complexities of SCD.

2 Improve access to specialised care:

- The research identified significant barriers to accessing specialised care for SCD patients, such as the limited availability of specialised clinics and long wait times. Establishing more specialised SCD clinics, particularly in areas with high prevalence rates, will ensure that patients receive timely and appropriate care.
- **Action:** Increase funding and resources for specialised clinics and create multidisciplinary teams that include haematologists, psychologists, and social workers to provide holistic care.

3 Implement patient-centred care models:

- Patient-centred care models prioritise the individual needs and preferences of patients, involving them in their own care decisions. This approach has been shown to improve patient satisfaction and health outcomes. For SCD patients, a tailored care plan that addresses both medical and psychosocial needs is essential.
 - **Action:** Develop and promote patient-centred care protocols, ensuring that patients are active participants in their treatment plans.
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6.3 Recommendations for Policymakers

1 Increase funding for SCD research and services:

- The research highlights a significant underfunding of SCD-related services and research in Ireland. Increasing financial support will enable more comprehensive research into SCD, leading to better treatment options and improved healthcare services.
- **Action:** Advocate for greater allocation of government and private sector funds towards SCD research and healthcare infrastructure.

2 Develop national guidelines for SCD management:

- There is a lack of standardised guidelines for the management of SCD in Ireland, leading to inconsistencies in care. National guidelines would ensure a uniform standard of care and improve the overall quality of healthcare services for SCD patients.
- **Action:** Collaborate with healthcare professionals and researchers to develop evidence-based national guidelines and ensure their implementation across all healthcare facilities.

3 Improve healthcare accessibility:

- Geographical and financial barriers significantly impact the ability of SCD patients to access necessary care. Expanding telemedicine services and providing financial support can mitigate these challenges.
- **Action:** Implement policies that support the expansion of telemedicine and introduce financial aid programmes to assist with the costs of treatment and travel for healthcare services.

6.4 Recommendations for Support Organisations

1 Enhance support networks:

- Support networks play a crucial role in the emotional and practical well-being of individuals with SCD. Strengthening these networks can provide much-needed emotional support, reduce feelings of isolation, and offer practical advice for managing the disease.
- **Action:** Develop and expand support groups, and organise regular meetings, workshops, and events for individuals with SCD and their families.

2 Increase public awareness and education:

- There is a significant lack of public awareness about SCD, which contributes to stigma and discrimination. Increasing public knowledge about SCD can foster a more inclusive and supportive environment.
- **Action:** There is a need to launch public awareness campaigns using various media platforms and collaborate with educational institutions to integrate SCD education into their curricula.

3 Advocate for patients' rights:

- Advocacy is essential to ensure that the rights of individuals with SCD are protected and that they receive equitable treatment in healthcare, education, and employment.
- **Action:** Work with policymakers and organisations to promote policies that protect individuals with SCD from discrimination and ensure their access to necessary services and support.

6.5 Recommendations for Future Studies

1 Incorporate additional data collection methods:

- Utilise other qualitative data collection methods such as focus groups, participant observations, and diaries to capture a broader range of experiences and provide more nuanced insights into the daily lives of individuals with SCD.

2 Explore Family and Carer Perspectives:

- Future research should include the perspectives of family members and carers to understand the broader impact of SCD on family dynamics and support systems. This could highlight additional areas where support is needed.

3 Intervention and Support Evaluation:

- Studies should evaluate the effectiveness of different interventions and support systems for individuals with SCD. This could include healthcare services, educational accommodations, employment support, and mental health resources.

4 Examine healthcare provider knowledge and training:

- Investigate the level of knowledge and training among healthcare providers regarding SCD. Understanding gaps in healthcare professionals' knowledge can inform the development of targeted training programmes to improve patient care.

5 Cross-Cultural Comparisons:

- Conduct comparative studies across different cultural and healthcare contexts to identify common challenges and unique issues faced by individuals with SCD in various settings. This could provide insights into best practices and successful interventions in different regions.

6 Policy and Advocacy Research:

- Future research should focus on the impact of existing policies on the lives of individuals with SCD and advocate for policy changes based on empirical evidence. Studies could explore the effectiveness of policy implementation and provide recommendations for policymakers.
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6.6 Conclusion

The recommendations outlined in this chapter are critical steps towards addressing the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ireland. By enhancing healthcare services, increasing public awareness, and providing comprehensive support systems, these recommendations aim to improve the quality of life and healthcare outcomes for those affected by SCD.

For healthcare providers, the emphasis on enhanced training, improved access to specialised care, and the implementation of patient-centred care models will equip medical professionals with the necessary skills and resources to provide empathetic and effective care. These measures will ensure that patients receive timely and holistic treatment, addressing both their medical and psychosocial needs.

Policy makers play a vital role in this initiative by increasing funding for SCD research and services, developing national guidelines for SCD management, and improving healthcare accessibility. These actions will create a more robust and equitable healthcare infrastructure, ensuring that all SCD patients receive consistent and high-quality care regardless of geographical and financial barriers.

Support organisations are also essential in this effort, as they provide crucial emotional and practical support. By enhancing support networks, increasing public awareness, and advocating for patients' rights, these organisations can help reduce stigma, promote inclusivity, and protect the rights of individuals with SCD.

In conclusion, the collaborative efforts of healthcare providers, policy makers, and support organisations are imperative to address the needs of SCD patients comprehensively. By implementing these recommendations, Ireland can make significant strides towards improving the lives of individuals with SCD, ensuring they receive the care, support, and respect they deserve.

Chapter
7.0
Conclusion
Esther Onolememen

7.1 Introduction

7.1.2. Summary of Key Findings

This research has provided a comprehensive exploration of the daily living experiences of individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in Ireland. Summary of key findings are as follows:

1 Severe Physical Complications:

- A Participants reported frequent vaso-occlusive crises, which cause severe pain and require urgent medical attention.
- B Many experienced organ damage and complications, such as stroke and acute chest syndrome, impacting their daily functioning and quality of life.
- C Chronic fatigue and physical limitations were common, affecting participants' ability to engage in regular activities and maintain employment.

2 Significant Mental Health Issues:

- High levels of anxiety and depression were prevalent among participants, often exacerbated by the unpredictability and severity of physical symptoms.
- The psychological burden of managing a chronic illness, coupled with frequent hospital visits and medical procedures, contributed to feelings of hopelessness and isolation.

3 Widespread Stigma and Discrimination:

- Participants reported experiences of stigma and discrimination in various settings, including healthcare, education, and employment.
- Misunderstanding and lack of awareness about SCD among peers and professionals often led to negative judgments and inadequate support.

4 Barriers to Accessing Healthcare:

- Limited availability of specialised care and long wait times for medical appointments were significant barriers.
- Financial constraints, including the cost of treatments and medications, further restricted access to necessary healthcare services.
- Geographic disparities in healthcare provision meant that those living in rural areas faced additional challenges in accessing specialised care.

5 Impact on Education:

- Frequent absences due to medical appointments and hospitalisations negatively impacted participants' academic performance and progress.
- Participants felt unsupported by educational institutions, which often lacked understanding and accommodations for their condition.
- The stress and fatigue associated with SCD made it difficult for participants to keep up with their studies, leading to lower academic achievement and limited career prospects.

6 Employment Challenges:

- Many participants had to choose lower-impact jobs or self-employment to manage their health alongside work commitments.
- Lack of accommodations and understanding from employers led to job insecurity and additional stress.
- Participants frequently faced difficulty disclosing their condition to employers due to fear of discrimination and misunderstanding.

6 Role of Family and Social Support:

- Family members, particularly mothers, often provided crucial emotional and practical support, although this came at a significant cost to their well-being.

- Strong support networks, including friends and community groups, were vital in helping participants cope with the challenges of SCD.
- The emotional support from these networks helped mitigate the feelings of isolation and provided a sense of belonging and understanding.

7.2 Contributions to Knowledge

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing detailed insights into the lived experiences of individuals with SCD in Ireland. It highlights the multifaceted nature of the challenges they face and underscores the need for targeted interventions to improve their quality of life. The research also identifies critical gaps in the current healthcare system and offers practical recommendations for addressing these issues.

7.3 Implications for Practice and Policy

The findings of this research have significant implications for both practice and policy.

Healthcare Practice:

- **Enhanced Training and Education:** Training healthcare professionals about SCD is crucial to improving patient care and outcomes. This includes understanding the medical aspects and the cultural context of the patients.
- **Patient-Centred Care:** Adopting patient-centred care models ensures that treatment plans are tailored to the individual needs and preferences of SCD patients, which can significantly enhance their quality of life.
- **Community Support Organisations:** The role of community support organisations is vital in improving care for individuals with SCD. These organisations provide essential services such as emotional support, educational resources, and

advocacy. Strengthening these organisations can lead to better patient outcomes by offering a support network that complements medical care. These groups can also bridge gaps between patients and healthcare providers, ensuring that patients' voices are heard, and their needs are met effectively.

Healthcare Policy:

- **Funding for SCD Research and Services:** Policymakers should prioritise funding for SCD research and healthcare services to address the identified gaps. Investing in research can lead to better treatment options and improved healthcare infrastructure.
- **National Guidelines for SCD Management:** Developing and implementing national guidelines for SCD management will ensure consistent care across the country, improving overall healthcare service quality for SCD patients.
- **Healthcare Accessibility:** Addressing healthcare accessibility through telemedicine and financial support policies can significantly alleviate the burden on SCD patients. Policies should be designed to make healthcare services more accessible, especially for those in remote areas.

7.4 Study Limitations

1 Small Sample Size:

- The study involved a small, purposive sample of seven participants. While this allowed for in-depth exploration of individual experiences, it limits the generalisability of the findings to the broader population of individuals with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in Ireland. We recognised the small sample size was necessary as a pilot study as our aim was to build on the findings of this study in future studies. The six research assistants were necessary to understand the full range of issues for the pilot study and the primary researcher needed the team to set a research agenda in an unbiased manner.

2 Potential Bias in Self-Reporting:

- The data collection relied on self-reported experiences through semi-structured interviews. Participants may have had recall bias or may have underreported their experiences due to personal perceptions or the desire to present themselves in a certain way.

3 Single Method of Data Collection:

- The study used semi-structured in-depth interviews as the sole method of data collection. While this method provided rich, qualitative data, incorporating additional methods such as focus groups or observational studies could have offered a more comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences.

4 Lack of Longitudinal Perspective:

- The study provides a snapshot of participants' experiences at a single point in time. A longitudinal approach, following participants over an extended period, could provide deeper insights into the evolving nature of living with SCD and the long-term impact on education and employment.

5 Limited Diversity of Participants:

- The sample primarily consisted of young adults aged 18 to 30, which may not capture the full spectrum of experiences across different age groups, and within the family dynamics where family members or caregivers are involved. Also, older individuals with SCD may face different challenges that were not addressed in this study. The focus on young people was to capture a snapshot of a growing population of young black Irish people with sickle cell, most of whom have experienced the transition phase from children's services to adult services, and are also at stages where they are navigating education, and employment independently.

7.5 Conclusion

Addressing the multifaceted needs of individuals with SCD in Ireland requires a coordinated effort from healthcare providers, policymakers, support organisations, and the broader community. The recommendations outlined in this research provide a comprehensive roadmap for improving the quality of life for those affected by SCD. Enhanced training for healthcare professionals, improved access to specialised care, patient-centred care models, increased funding for SCD research, development of national guidelines, and better healthcare accessibility are critical steps towards this goal.

Additionally, strengthening support networks, increasing public awareness, and advocating for patients' rights are essential for reducing stigma and providing comprehensive care. The significant impact of SCD on education and employment highlights the need for tailored support systems and policies that accommodate the unique challenges faced by individuals with chronic illnesses.

This study revealed the need for continued research and advocacy in SCD care and management and emphasised how essential it is to ensure that the voices of individuals with SCD are heard and that their needs are met. This study serves as a foundation for future work aimed at achieving these goals and fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment for individuals with SCD in Ireland. By implementing these recommendations, significant progress can be made in improving the lives of those affected by SCD, ensuring they receive the care, support, and respect they deserve.

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Appendix One Interview Guide

Research Outline

To explore the daily living experiences of people with sickle cell, and its impact on education and employment in Ireland, crafting articulate research questions is essential. These questions should aim to uncover not only the direct experiences of individuals with sickle cell disease (SCD) but also the broader socio-economic implications, challenges, and support systems available or needed in Ireland.

Start with Introduction:

- Clarify understanding of research purpose
- Clarify consent to record interview
- What is your name
- How old
- How many in household or family composition
- Background of family and circumstance

Here are several research questions that could guide a comprehensive study in this area:

1 Understanding Daily Living Experiences:

- How do individuals with sickle cell in Ireland describe their daily living experiences and challenges related to their condition?
- What are the most common coping strategies employed by people with sickle cell in Ireland to manage their symptoms and maintain their quality of life?

2 Impact on Education:

- How does sickle cell disease affect the educational attainment and school attendance of individuals in Ireland?
- What accommodations and supports are currently available for students with sickle cell in Irish educational institutions, and how effective are these measures from the perspective of the students?

- To what extent do educational professionals in Ireland (teachers, administrators, and support staff) feel prepared to meet the needs of students with sickle cell disease?

3 Impact on Employment:

- What are the employment rates among individuals with sickle cell in Ireland, and how do these compare with the general population?
- How does sickle cell disease impact job performance, career progression, and job satisfaction among affected individuals in Ireland?
- What workplace accommodations and supports are most beneficial for employees with sickle cell, and to what extent are these accommodations being provided?

4 Healthcare and Social Support:

- How do individuals with sickle cell in Ireland navigate the healthcare system, and what barriers do they face in accessing care?
- Do you have much awareness about your condition?
- What treatment are you currently on? How often do you take treatment?
- How often are you in crisis? If in a crisis where do you go? How often do you attend routine care?
- What role do social support networks (including families, communities, and support groups) play in the lives of people with sickle cell in Ireland?
- What are your thoughts on adult care in comparison to children care?
- Policy and Awareness:
 - What policies are currently in place in Ireland to support individuals with sickle cell in the realms of education and employment, and how effective are these policies from the perspectives of those affected?

- How aware are the general public and professionals (in healthcare, education, and employment sectors) of sickle cell disease and its impacts on individuals' lives?
- Do you receive disability allowance?
 - If yes how was the application process?
 - If no, do you think people living with SCD should receive it?
- Do you have a medical card?
 - Was it hard to access?

To round up:

- Of all things discussed today, what area does your sickle cell impact your life the most?

These questions aim to illuminate the multifaceted experiences of individuals with sickle cell in Ireland, focusing on their daily lives, educational and employment opportunities, and the efficacy of current support systems and policies.

Gender Distribution of Study Participants

Education Level of Study Participants

Appendix Two

Participant Consent Form

Study	Exploring the daily living experiences of people with sickle cell, and the impact on education and employment in Ireland.	
Principal Investigator and Supervisor	Name: Esther Onolememen Email: esther.onolememen@sicklecellsocietyireland.org Phone: 087 989 0691	
Research Assistant Name	Name: Email: info@sicklecellsocietyireland.org Phone:	
Please tick appropriate box	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I confirm that I have read and understood the information leaflet and have had time to consider whether I wish to partake in this study. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No • I understand that my name will not be identified as part of this research and should any information from my interview be used, it will be in anonymised form. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No • I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No • I understand that as part of this research, I will be participating in an interview which will be audio-taped and transcribed. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No • I understand that (research assistant) and Esther Onolememen (principal investigator) will have access to and responsibility for data protection of any information given by me as part of this study until publication. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No 	
Participant Name		
Signature		
Date		

Appendix Three

Research Study Information

Study	Exploring the daily living experiences of people with sickle cell, and the impact on education and employment in Ireland.
Principal Investigator and Supervisor	Name: Esther Onolememen Email: esther.onolememen@sicklecellsocietyireland.org Phone: 087 989 0691
Research Assistant	Name: Email: info@sicklecellsocietyireland.org Phone:

Background

Sickle cell disease is a chronic condition that can cause frequent pain episodes, fatigue, and other health complications. These can significantly impact a person's ability to engage in daily activities and maintain regular attendance at school or work. Sickle cell disease predominantly affects people of African descent in Ireland. Sickle cell is relatively new in Ireland and the lack of awareness means that some aspects of sickle cell patients and their family's daily functioning are still unknown to not only the government but also the healthcare professionals. The study will interview patients living with sickle cell and will explore their daily living experiences in how they cope with navigating life's journey in Ireland and how this impacts their access to education and employment.

Aims and Objectives: To gain more understanding of the factors influencing how people living with sickle cell navigate daily living we are currently recruiting interested participants for this very unique and ground-breaking study as well as volunteers willing to be a part of this journey. The interview will take place in a private confidential setting, with an option of using Zoom. Participants will have a chance to ask questions they may have during and after interviews. The interview will be audiotaped and kept electronically with access granted to only the research assistant and principal investigator. All electronic data will be destroyed after the research duration.

Conduct of Study: This study will commence its recruitment process in November 2023. Interviews are targeted to commence in February 2023. The research will include conducting individual interviews with patients.

Who can apply? Patients who have confirmed sickle cell diagnosis and are over 18 years of age. Insights from carers are also accepted.

Acknowledgements

This research is kindly funded by the Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth, for the International Decade for People of African Descent (IDPAD).

Appendix Four

Distress Protocol for SCD Research Interviews

This protocol outlines steps to be taken if a participant becomes distressed during the interview phase of this study. Before any interview begins, all participants will receive information about designated support persons (e.g., gatekeepers) and relevant community support. If a participant becomes distressed during the interview, this information will be given again.

Strategies to Assist Distressed Participants

If a participant becomes uncomfortable or distressed while discussing their experiences, the interviewer will take the following actions:

- 1** Terminate the Interview: The interviewer will suggest ending the interview if the participant shows signs of distress.
- 2** Cease the Interview: If the participant agrees, the interview will be immediately stopped.
- 3** Provide Immediate Support: The interviewer will spend time with the participant, offering support and discussing their concerns within the interviewer's capabilities.
- 4** Recommend Further Support: The participant will be advised to speak with their community leader, designated support person, or other appropriate community supports.
- 5** Follow-Up: The interviewer will make a follow-up phone call the next day to check on the participant's well-being and reiterate the available support information.
- 6** Ongoing Distress: If the participant's distress continues, they will be encouraged to contact their general practitioner (GP).

Contact Details for Participants

Contact information for designated support persons (e.g., community leaders) and available community supports will be provided to all prospective and actual study participants.

Conclusion

Although it is unlikely that these interviews will cause distress, it is the interviewer's duty of care to ensure these strategies are in place before starting the interviews to support participants effectively.

SCSI
Sickle Cell Society Ireland

 Reme Onolememe
Sickle Cell Research Foundation

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